

A Spatial Analysis of Ethiopia's 2015 Drought: New Directions in Predicting High Damage, Low Frequency Cereal Crop Loss

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Abstract

Without critical analysis, many policymakers perceive that droughts affect countries in a relatively random fashion. In other words, the vagaries of rainfall deficits impact several parts of the country without any discernible pattern. In this study, we provide various empirical evidence of localized crop damage clusters in the 2015 growing season. Three principal results include, using a time series data fusion model, predicating the existence of high crop damage neighborhoods, early crop season productivity forecasts ("Now Casting"), and a binary machine learning model that seeks to explain crop specific, large damage (>25%), localized events. Among many issues, this paper reveals that 2015 drought areas are highly correlated to clusters that suffered damage in previous years. In other words, previous high damage areas were the most likely areas to suffer from the 2015 drought. Furthermore, these areas do not fit neatly into existing administrative areas. This in turn suggests that any of international emergency relief agencies designated drought areas may have a variation in actual impacts. Put simply, our models suggest a great deal of intra-administrative area variation. Finally, the high damage cluster areas are in relatively lower production areas suggesting that 2015 crop failures, while devastating to the local communities, had a smaller impact on national production figures. To explore the impact of these local droughts and management techniques on output per hectare, we develop a panel regression utilizing sub-kebele level agricultural survey data, and remotely sensed data on greenness, precipitation and measures of evaporative demand. A set of models is created to provide mid-season estimates ("Now Casting") of output per hectare for maize, wheat and barley, and obtain R^2 between 0.39 and 0.35 at the sub-kebele level. These "Now Casting" estimates can be used by the policy makers to make early estimates of total production, or to help identify areas in need of intervention. We also find crop specific responses to a variety of management practices, and climate conditions with R^2 between 0.47 and 0.31 at the sub-kebele level. We believe these models could be used to help monitor and predict yields for disaster response teams and policy makers to use, particularly with further development and integration of the newly available 30m Harmonized Landsat Sentinel (HLS) data set. Radical improvements could be obtained with the newly available HLS data due to both its higher resolution, and radiometric sensitivity. We further utilize our agricultural survey and remotely sensed data to develop machine learning models aimed at predicting substantial crop losses (>25%) due to drought. These models predict, on an independent sample, substantial drought damage with over 95 percent accuracy, with Kappa coefficients in the mid to high 60s. We consider these findings substantial because they reach accuracy levels meaningful for policy, but also because they are based largely on course (250m) resolution data and agricultural survey data that is often dismissed in the research community.

1 Introduction

The ability to monitor and predict crop yields in developing countries is critical to the successful adaptation to changes in climate. Increased temperatures and variability has already been linked to losses in maize and wheat yields (-3.8 and -5.5% respectively) and crop prices (Lobell, Schlenker, and Costa-Roberts 2011). Although much effort has been placed on modeling the spatial distribution of these shifts, less effort has been placed on how yields vary across space and time especially in a longitudinal setting (Ray et al. 2015). Advances in remote sensing provide avenues to monitor agricultural crop health at high spatial and temporal resolution. However, our ability to monitor changes in plant productivity is still limited in the more complex environments common to many developing countries (Mann and Warner 2015).

Ethiopia's agriculture is characterized by smallholder farmers dependent on rain-fed crops with approximately one percent of farmers having access to irrigation (Mann and Warner 2015). Meanwhile, projections of climate change point to increasing severity and duration of extreme weather events, including drought (Parry et al. 2007). As such, Ethiopia's farmers are particularly vulnerable to inter- and intra-annual variation in rainfall. Although there has been substantial effort in improving the modeling and observation of weather and climate, observations of ground based measurements of agricultural outcomes and practices is limited. One could argue without understanding, in detail, the impacts of changes in weather and climate on households' agriculture and well-being, much of climate science will have minimal impact on our ability to mitigate and adapt to these changes. We believe that integrating data, from a variety of sources, including remote sensed, GIS and traditional household survey data provides necessary synergies to explain the effects of climate change on farmer welfare and to help observe how farmers adapt. For example, every year Ethiopia's Central Statistical Agency (CSA) carries out one of the largest household agricultural surveys in the world. The Agricultural Sample Survey (AgSS) captures data from over 45,000 households, and provides a critical view of agricultural yields, extension outreach, and farmers' practices in a spatially explicit manner. While significant analysis has been performed using survey data sets, far less research has been performed using this data combined with other sources.

Remote sensing based efforts to characterize the extent, cultivation practices, and productivity of global croplands has a long history. Substantial progress has been made in mapping cropland extent, crop types, irrigation status, cropping intensity, and productivity from remotely sensed imagery particularly for developed countries. Initial efforts (e.g. LACIE and AgRISTARS) primarily utilized remotely sensed imagery to characterize the spatial extent and growth stage of crops, but relied on models driven chiefly by meteorological information to predict crop yield (Idso, Jackson, and Reginato 1977; Doraiswamy et al. 2003). However, the biophysical link between canopy spectral reflectance and net primary production has long been established (Tucker and Sellers 1986); indicating that satellite measurements could play a role in determining crop yield directly. A wide number of studies have documented highly explanatory empirical relationships between satellite measures such as NDVI (in many forms: growing season maximum and mean, seasonally integrated, etc.) and yields for a variety of crops, particularly at *regional* scales (Rasmussen 1992; Benedetti and Rossini 1993; Funk and Budde 2009; Becker-Reshef, Vermote, et al. 2010; Becker-Reshef, Justice, et al. 2010; Mkhabela et al. 2011). Because certain crop growth stages are particularly critical for final yield (Butler and Huybers 2015), improved results are often seen when remotely sensed data are used to characterize crop phenology (Bolton and Friedl 2013). However, it is clear that remotely sensed data has limitations.

Critically, the AgSS survey data provides us with observations of crop yields and losses for all of Ethiopia's major crops, as well as a snapshot of farmers' practices. This research focuses on the five principal cereal crops grown in Ethiopia (Maize, Wheat, Teff, Barley and Sorghum). Meanwhile, observations from remotely sensed data provides us with extensive data concerning rainfall, vegetation properties, and temperature amongst others. When combined, observations from the AgSS and remotely sensed data provide rich information, coupling observations of farming outcomes with dense observations of properties such as plant greenness or the timing of rains. This data fusion allows us to create models that, once trained, can predict crop yields and losses solely with the use of remotely sensed observations from space or weather stations.

The main objectives of this paper are to create a suite of models that can a) provide reliable estimates of yields based on remotely sensed data early in the growing season, b) reveal insights into the impacts of farm management, and c) lay the groundwork for a system that is capable of using higher resolution (such as the

forthcoming Harmonized Landsat Sentinel data) at a national scale. We also augment a suite of algorithms used to extract, summarize, and organize remotely sensed data and prepare it for spatiotemporal analysis (Mann et al. 2018).

1.1 The State of Drought

Spurred by a long history of monsoon failures across the Sahel, forecasters and aid teams anxiously watched eastern Africa at the onset of a significant El Nino event in late 2014. Reports of below average rainfalls in 2015-17 particularly across the low lying pastoral communities and of south-eastern Ethiopia triggered an international effort to provide food aid to roughly 8.5 million people in the summer of 2017 (ReliefWeb 2017; UNOCHA 2017). The understated response from the Ethiopian government had led to accusations that the government was downplaying the severity of the drought as early as 2016 (Schemm 2016; Schemm 2017). Despite the reality of a severe and crippling drought in food insecure low-lying areas, there is little sign of food shortages nationally, with a recent study observing no significant change in grain prices throughout the country (Bachewe, Yimer, and Minten 2016). The lack of a price response would indicate that while food insecure areas were hit heavily by water shortages largely effecting livestock, the most productive highland areas were largely unaffected or triggering only minor losses. Our results confirm this hypothesis. Contrary to early rapid assessments performed by Tufts that losses of production over 18% of production were to be expected, research presented here supports both the price research and the later AgSS cereal production estimate of losses of less than two percent. This does not that lessen the fact that there was catastrophic crop loss in several marginally productive areas. Put another way, the 2015 drought was far more likely to impact existing PSNP woredas (targeted for social protection) than AGP woredas (high growth potential). Despite international concern, conditions up until the 2016-2017 growing season may have been largely handled by domestic resources and trade flows, therefore requiring shifts in distribution rather than a large-scale international intervention. A review of rainfall data demonstrates regional impacts consistent with reported cereal crop loss.

Figure 1: Median rainfall per 10 day period 2010-2015 compared to 2015 & 2016 actual

Looking at Figure 1 we can see the spatiotemporal patterns of rainfall across Ethiopia. The top panel (a) reports the median total rain fall per 10-day period during each month (in mm). Here we can see the onset of the heavy rains during the Meher growing season, and the decline near harvest in October. In panels (b-c) we can see the deviation from this norm for the years 2015 and 2016 (in mm). The only striking shortfall is July of 2015, and patchy isolated declines through August that year. The year 2016, by comparison shows indications of generally above average rainfall. These figures demonstrate the spatial heterogeneity of rainfall over time. Both years show small areas that interchange between having above or below average rainfall. The erratic nature of these rains points to the critical nature of their timing, with rainfall being more important during critical growth stages like germination and flowering. If rains fail during critical periods, even small shortfalls can precipitate significant losses. Therefore Ethiopia, like many rainfall dependent countries has and will continue to be prone to localized and occasionally wide-spread yield losses. On average, AgSS reports average cereal crop losses of about 10% per annum averaged at the sub-kebele level. Most of this damage can be attributed to vagaries in the weather (flooding, hail, drought, among others).

Figure 2: Total Major Cereal Crop Production 2010-2015 (by zone, weighted)

Aggregated zonal cereal production¹ is presented in Figure 2. The graph demonstrates the relative stability of total production for 2010 to 2015, especially for the top 20 zones (labeled above). We can see that the total production of each zone (as indicated by the width of each bar) generally remains steady or increases over time. Moreover, we can see that the rank of zones (as indicated by the plot order, bottom being lowest rank, top being highest rank) remains surprisingly steady despite the exogenous shock of drought in the 2015 growing season. Moreover, reported total production increases year over year despite the influence of the drought. As we will see below this might point to two factors, farmers moving to more drought tolerant crops, or more simply just the limited nature of this droughts effect on high production areas. While aggregating the five crops by weight has some important methodological concerns, the weight was used to measure relative loss in production rather than monetary value of losses. Incorporating a price index would speak to monetary value but the price changes might reflect market movements over drought effects. For this reason, simple weight was used.

Figure 3 details three time series sets of data for all major regions depicting the drought, in the top panel (a) the mean percentage of planted area damaged by damage type for all crops, the middle panel (b) the percentage of area planted in each major crop, in the bottom panel (c) median output per hectare (OPH) in quintiles for each major crop. Looking at panel (a) the most obvious feature is the sudden spike in reports of mean drought damage, particularly for Tigray. Tigray reported drought damage, on average, to just over 25% of planted area. That being said, both Amhara and Oromia reported average drought damage of almost 20%. Although a much lower level of loss, Amhara and Oromia both have significantly higher arable land and it therefore appears they experienced milder losses across a much larger area. As discussed later, the variation in these regions suggest concentrated high loss neighborhoods with predominate non-affected areas. Beyond the drought effects, relatively consistent reports of losses due to pests and poor management (poor timing of planting, failure to control weeds etc) are reported across all years. During the marked spike in reports of drought damage in the 2015 planting season (covering harvest in 2016), we see a few important responses.

¹This graph reflects a simple aggregation, by weight, of the five principal cereal crops in Ethiopia (Wheat, Barley, Maize, Sorghum and Teff).

First, although slight, farmers increased the percentage of area planted in drought tolerant crops such as maize and sorghum. This is particularly true in Tigray, where the drought hit hardest. These preliminary results raise interesting questions concerning drought and farmer response and may be important for understanding potential effects of longer term climate change. Second, we see that although some regions saw declines in median output per hectare, these losses are largely offset by gains in other crops or by the steady increase in output per hectare since 2010.

Figure 3: Drought in one graph 2010-2015

Figure 4: Reported Drought Damage by Zone 2015 with Elevation

In Figure 4 we see that drought may have been elusive in 2015 for critical parts of the growing regions. The strongest effects of the drought were limited to the eastern reaches of Tigray, the upper and eastern slopes of the Wollo highlands, and eastern-most Ahmar Mountains. *Notice that the worst drought struck zones were in the rainshadow² of Ras Dashen, Ethiopia’s highest peak, and along the upper ridges of the Simien and Ahmar mountains.* The figure indicates that Ethiopia has an extraordinary topography, with jagged mountains, rugged hillsides, and narrow canyons all being graded and tilled for agriculture. This complex terrain in turn leads to complex micro-climates in many ways much like those found in California’s Sierra Mountains and coastal influence areas. Rain shadows, elevation, strong inversion layers, monsoonal rain, complex wind patterns all lead to an extremely heterogeneous growing environment, where conditions on one side of the mountain could be completely different than on the other.

2 Methods

2.1 Data Sources

2.1.1 Survey Data - Agricultural Sample Survey Data (2010-2015)

Survey data was obtained from Ethiopia’s Central Statistical Agency’s (CSA) Agricultural Sample Survey (AgSS) and was chosen for its annual collection, spatial coverage, and unique sampling structure through these six crop years. The AgSS is an annually collected government administered large-scale survey tasked with measuring agricultural production in Ethiopia at the zonal level.³ The survey interviews approximately 45,000

²A rain shadow is a dry area on the leeward side of a mountain. The mountains block the passage of rain-producing weather and produce a shadow of dryness behind them.

³Beyond the nation, Ethiopia has four official levels of administrative areas. These include, in order of geographic size, regions, zones, woredas and kebeles. There are approximately 12 regions, 88 zones, 690 woredas and 15,000 kebeles. For our purposes,

farmers per year on a range of farm management questions covering some basic demographics of the household as well as a range of questions concerning planting, harvesting and selling at the plot level. Typically, about 20 farm households are randomly sampled from small local village-level areas of approximately 200 households (the sub-kebele level). On average, based on population, approximately five of these sample areas exist at the kebele-level administration area. Although the figures vary widely, sub-kebeles are meant to approximate about 200 households per unit and the average kebele has around 1,000 households each. From this sampling frame, a random selection of about 2,200 sub-kebeles are chosen as a representative sub-sample for zonal level production projections of major agricultural production areas. Population weights are then applied to project agricultural production at the zonal level. For this study, we construct a panel data set over the six crop seasons identified because approximately 75% of all the same sub-kebeles were sampled by CSA over the six Meher crop seasons of interest. This effectively builds a base of five relatively favorable crop seasons, from 2010 to 2014, and allows for the drought effects of 2015 as a study in contrast in terms of this significant weather event. The sample is with replacement and therefore representative of the sub-kebele but not a true panel because the same farmers were not chosen. In addition, no sampling weights are applied because we have omitted approximately 25% of the sample and are generally most interested in the localized effects.

While this study collected data on the five principal Ethiopian field crops (teff, wheat, maize, barley, sorghum), because of their predominant importance in value terms for Ethiopia as well as their geographically wide-spread adoption, the analysis should therefore be placed within this context. This study covers the drought effects of only these five crops and not all agricultural production. In other words, when we outline percentages of crop losses we are referring to losses of only these five crops and not total output in the country. We have no reason to believe that these are not generally representative of all crop production, in terms of the drought, but a more detailed analysis would be needed to make this assertion.

The principal unit of analysis is the sub-kebele and all relevant CSA data is aggregated to this level. The survey data represents an amalgamation of all 20 households as a single representative farmer, we refer to as a “super-farmer.” This was done for a variety of reasons including the fragmented plot farming system common in Ethiopia as well as CSA data collection methodology. More specifically, CSA data collection methodology relies on crop cuts to estimate productivity at the local level. Depending on the actual number of farmers growing the specific crop, CSA collects up to five different individual farmer crop cuts, averages the yields, and projects this figure onto all plot areas for that crop in the sub-kebele. In this way, individual plot level yields are not able to be determined and, consequently, household level estimates are not possible. Additionally, while the level of the pixel used for the remote sensing data is relatively granular ($6,250 \text{ m}^2$), cost and logistic considerations make plot level estimations prohibitive in this research. Therefore, the data from 20 farmers is aggregated to a single super-farmer resulting in 1,780 observations sampled from the sub-kebele area (approximately $23,900,000 \text{ m}^2$) over a six-year period. The total number of observations collected is about 10,680 but will vary in sample size depending on the crop choice (i.e.. some areas do not grow all five designated crops). A breakdown of each super-farmer is done with aggregated non-crop related information combined with the specificity of the individual crop chosen. More precisely, several variables are consistent across all five crop choices (elevation, proportional numbers of male and female household heads, total land area, etc.) and others are crop specific (use of fertilizer, seed, etc.). Each crop year was checked for consistency, cleaned and aggregated to the sub-kebele level. The six years were then aggregated and merged with other data to develop the panel data set. Importantly, for our analysis, we chose specific variables to reflect farmer management decisions and other actions affecting yields. For data cleaning, we Winsorize yield estimates capping them at the 90th percentile, and we also drop any sub-kebele unit that has less than 4 years of data from regressions.

2.1.2 Remotely Sensed Data - Greenness, Precipitation and Evaporation

2.1.2.1 Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

Considering the relatively small scale of agriculture in this region we use 250m vegetation products from the MODIS satellites. Vegetation indices are obtained from two 16-day MODIS products (MOD13Q1, MYD13Q1)

we use the sub-kebele, not recognized as a geographic region for administrative purposes, but commonly used for statistical sampling and are roughly based on population. There are over 75,000 sub-kebeles in the country.

from the Aqua and Terra satellites (Didan and Huete 2006). Due to the staggered nature of acquisition, these products are treated as partially overlapping windows representing 8-day periods (Doraiswamy, Stern, and Akhmedov 2007). We find that the combination of these two products provides a stable and informative time series.

For the sake of simplicity and replicability, we focus on the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and examine its predictive power using panel econometric techniques. NDVI is sensitive to the amount of chlorophyll in any given pixel and is commonly used to estimate plant productivity and health in agricultural applications (Mann and Warner 2017; Mann and Warner 2015; Funk and Budde 2009). After removal of snow, cloud and other flagged low-quality cells, we remove all non-agricultural cells through the use of the 500m MODIS land cover product (MCD12Q1) for the appropriate year.

2.1.2.2 Water Availability Variables

In order to estimate the effects of precipitation (PPT) on our crop production models the Climate Hazards Group Infrared Precipitation Station (CHIRPS) data was included. Data is collected as total precipitation by dekadal (Funk et al. 2015). A dekadal represents three periods each month, the first two periods being 10 days each, and the third being any remaining days of that month.

Hydrological availability of water and available energy for plant growth have been shown in previous research to be important factors in crop models and are therefore included here. For this reason, we include monthly estimates of potential evaporation (PET) and actual evapotranspiration anomaly (ETA). Actual evapotranspiration (AET) is the sum of transpired water through plants plus evaporation from soils and water surfaces. In other words, it is the total amount of water moved through a system. AET is a correlated with vascular plant productivity, biomass accumulation and regrowth (Major 1967; Mann et al. 2016). The ETA variable used in this study is the current AET compared to the 2003-2013 mean. ETA therefore is a proxy for drought as low current values of AET would correspond to reductions either in available energy to move water, or water itself. Potential evapotranspiration (PET) is an estimate of the total amount of water that could be moved through the system if water was not a limiting factor. As such it is an ideal indicator of available (or excessive) energy in the form of energy or heat, but also includes the impact of wind speed, pressure, and humidity amongst others. PET can be though more simply as a proxy for temperature. Both ETA and PET are available for download through FEWS NET (2017).

2.1.3 Variable Definitions

The following section outlines the definitions of variables used from the AgSS, GIS and remotely sensed data:

Table 1: AgSS variable names & descriptions

Name	Description
Prefixes	
MAIZE_	Variables based on maize plots
WHEAT_	Variables based on wheat plots
BARLEY_	Variables based on barley plots
SORGHUM_	Variables based on sorghum plots
TEFF_	Variables based on teff plots
Postfixes and Other	
_diff	First difference
lag(X,1)	One year lag of variable X
AgSS Variables	
OPH_W	Winsorized (95th) values of output per hectare (quintals)
IMSEED	Quantity of improved seeds (kg)
IMSEED_P	Percentage of planted area planted with improved seeds
FERT_CHEMICAL_AREA_P	Percentage of area treated with chemical fertilizers

Name	Description
Fert_Amt_Per_Area	Quantity of chemical fertilizer used per unit area
DAMAGE_AREA_P	Percentage of area reported as having ‘damage’ (all causes)
DAMAGE_DROUGHT_AREA_P	Percentage of area reported as having ‘damage’, (drought)
EXTAREA	Area reported as being covered by extension services
Other Geographic Variables	
dist_pp50k	Distance from nearest populated place with greater than 50k persons (km)
dist_rcap	Distance from nearest regional capital (km)
elevation	Elevation (m)

Table 2: Remotely sensed variable names & descriptions

Name	Description
Prefixes	
G_	Calculated from Meher growing season values
A_	Calculated from all calendar year values
ETA_	Actual evapotranspiration
PET_	Potential evapotranspiration
PPT_	Precipitation
Postfixes and Other	
_diff	First difference
lag(X,1)	One year lag of variable X
NDVI Basic Summary Statistics	
G(A)_mn	Meher (Annual) growing season mean values of NDVI
G(A)_min	Meher (Annual) growing season min values of NDVI
G(A)_max	Meher (Annual) maximum values of NDVI
G(A)_height	Meher (Annual) difference between G(A)_max and G(A)_min
G(A)_sd	Meher (Annual) standard deviation in values of NDVI
G_plant_date	Estimated date of Meher planting based on NDVI phenology
G_harvest_date	Estimated date of Meher harvest based on NDVI phenology
season_length	Difference between G_plant_date and G_harvest_date
Other Basic Summary Statistics	
PET(ETA,PPT)_G_mn	Meher growing season mean values of PET (or ETA, PPT) values for the Meher growing season defined by G_plant_date and G_harvest_date
PET(ETA,PPT)_G_sd	Meher growing season sd of values for PET (or ETA, PPT) values for the Meher growing season defined by G_plant_date and G_harvest_date
Integrated Summary Statistics	
G_AUC	Rabi(Kharif) area under the curve of NDVI
G_AUC_v2	Rabi(Kharif) area under the curve of NDVI estimated by splines
G_AUC_leading	Area under the curve of NDVI for the ascending part of the curve during the Rabi(Kharif) season
G_AUC_trailing	Area under the curve of NDVI for the decreasing part of the curve during the Rabi(Kharif) season
Comparison to Norms	
G(PET,PPT)_AUC_diff_mn	Difference between current mean Meher NDVI (or PET, PET) and mean of historic values
G(PET,PPT)_AUC_diff_90th	Difference between current 90th percentile Meher NDVI (or PET, PET) and 90th percentile of historic values

2.2 Spatial Considerations of the Drought

Of critical importance to understanding droughts is determining both the spatial level of impact as well as the degree of crop loss. This paper performs this activity but also goes further and determines statistical patterns of annual crop damage that suggest predictability in where the drought effects are most likely to occur. Both time series and global/local statistical measures of clustering are used. Global measures of spatial autocorrelation evaluate whether or not observations of drought impacts are clustered (similar values are near each other), or whether they are spatially dispersed (dissimilar values are closer to each other) for the entire data set. Local measures of spatial autocorrelation can pick up on local concentrations of high (“hotspots”) or low values (“coldspots”).

2.2.1 Global Spatial Autocorrelation

Global Moran’s I depicts relative spatial autocorrelation for the entire area, where positive values convey clustering and negative values convey dispersion (dissimilar values are closer to each other), and can be mathematically depicted by formula 1: below.

(1)

$$I = \frac{n \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} z_i z_j}{S_0 \sum_{j=1}^N z_j^2}$$

where z_i is the difference between a location i and its mean ($x_i - \bar{X}$), w_{ij} is the spatial weight for feature i and its neighbors j , n is the number of features, and S_0 is the aggregate of all spatial weights in formula 2: below:

(2)

$$S_0 = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij}$$

Here we use neighborhood definition of a 25-km radius⁴ with a low decay rate of 0.05 power. This decay function suggests that about 85% of the total value of a neighbor 25 km away is used for weighting in the local neighborhood.

2.2.2 Hotspot Analysis

A typical method for identifying local spatial clustering is the Getis-Ord analysis that determines spatial clustering of values that exist at the statistical tails of a distribution. For our research, we identified hot neighborhoods that exist in the top 5% of a normal distribution of damage value and cold neighborhoods that exist in the bottom 5%. In other words, does a group neighborhood value statistically deviate from the global mean? In our case we defined a neighborhood as a 25-km radius from the centroid of the sub-kebele with a slight decay rate of 0.05 power.

Using Getis-Ord generates a Z-score and P-value for each sub-kebele in their respective neighborhood. Equation (3) demonstrates the spatial clustering with a 25-kilometer neighborhood and a small distance decay parameter as a weight. A high Z score and small P value for a feature indicates a significant hot spot. A low negative Z score and small P value indicates a significant cold spot. The higher (or lower) the Z score, the more intense the clustering. A Z score near zero means no spatial clustering. See formula 3 below.

(3)

$$G_i^* = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij}(d) x_j}{\sum_{j=1}^N x_j}$$

⁴The issue of what defines a neighbor is somewhat controversial in the spatial literature and the choice has important impacts on the analysis. For our purposes, 25 kilometers seemed reasonable from both expert opinion and fit the actual distribution of the data well.

$$(d) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } d_{ij} < d \text{ for all } i,j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

2.3 Estimating Crop Yields

2.3.1 Preprocessing

2.3.1.1 Data Aggregation

Because historical crop yields are only available at the level of given political units (sub-kebeles in this case), pixel-level NDVI data must be aggregated at this same level. In this study, we calculate the mean across the raw NDVI values for all available agricultural pixels at the sub-kebele-level and further extract statistics of interest from this resulting time-series (at a frequency of 8-days).

2.3.1.2 Summarizing Temporal Data

One of the primary challenges in utilizing high-frequency time series (8-day NDVI) to estimate low-frequency events (seasonal yields) is in reconciling this temporal mismatch when formalizing the relationship between sources of data. In general, low-frequency properties must be extracted from the high-frequency time series that may be relevant to characterize and identify important aspects of plant phenology across the growing season that affect crop yields. In this paper we aim to capture relevant phenological features of wheat through 41 metrics summarizing 8-day NDVI data. These metrics cover Meher growing season statistics, spanning the estimated planting date until harvest date. These plant and harvest dates are estimated on a sub-kebele basis, therefore differences in timing due to elevation, crop choice or other management considerations should be captured.

We estimate three classes of statistics across each of these two distinct periods: summary statistics (e.g. mean, max, variance); integrated summary statistics (e.g. area under the curve for the first half of the growing season); and deviation from the norm statistics (e.g. deviations of a given statistic from its 90th historical percentile).

2.3.2 “Now Casting” - Estimation Strategy

One primary use for these data is for early season estimation of crop yields. Although AgSS provides invaluable estimates of agricultural productivity on an annual basis, the lag between data collection and release is substantial. The timing is important for potential policy interventions in the case of crop booms or shortfalls. This gap leaves substantial need for timely and relatively accurate first-order estimates of crop yields. Motivated by preliminary panel regression results reported in the Appendix, we find that reasonable estimates of output per hectare can be created around mid-season. Where ‘mid-season’ is defined by reaching the maximum NDVI greenness value and is approximately three to four months after planting.

2.3.2.1 Panel Regression for “Now-Casting”

Compared to cross-sectional approaches, panel analysis can substantially increase the degree of observed variance over both space and time. For instance, in our current application, the integration of sub-kebeles (with $n = 1752$) over the 2010-2015 sample period ($t = 6$), results in a substantially larger data set ($N \sim 10,500$), allowing for a much greater flexibility and degrees of freedom in the modelling of the issue of interest. Here we include a series of variables that can be calculated in the first half of the growing season including contemporaneous and lagged values, Zonal fixed effects, as well as a lagged value of output per hectare. Here we estimate a series of random effect models of the following form 4:

(4)

$$Y_{ict} = \alpha_i + Y_{ict-1} + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k X_{it} + \mu_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

where Y_{itc} is the output per hectare (OPH) for crop c for sub-kebele i for year t , α is the average output per hectare for sample population (all major growing regions), Y_{t-1} is the lagged value of OPH, $\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k X_{it}$ is the sum of all K coefficient estimates β_k for all variables X , where X comprises all variables that are available at the mid-growing season, μ_i is the sub-kebele specific random effect that measures the difference between the average OPH at sub-kebele i and the average OPH in all major growing regions. The term ϵ_{it} is the individual-specific effect, which can be described as the deviation of the i th OPH from the average for that year.

We present preliminary “Now-Casting” results from panel regressions on output per hectare for Ethiopia’s major crops *here*. While the early estimation of crop yields may be of interest to policy makers, our data also provides us with an ability to identify those areas experiencing substantial losses at the close of any given season.

2.4 Predicting Crop Losses from Drought

Another important emphasis of this project is to see if remotely sensed data on greenness, precipitation, or evapotranspiration and the zone code can be used in conjunction with household surveys to predict the location and/or extent of damages before the AgSS survey results are released. In this vein we aim to utilize advances from machine learning (random forests) to accurately predict substantial crop damages for all major crops. We define our dependent variable, ‘substantial’ losses due to drought, as farmer reported losses of 25% or more. Two types of models are then run for each crop, one, a “national-level” model is trained on all observations for the major growing regions, and a second group of “region-level” models where each model is trained from data in a specific region. Specifically, our model takes the following form:

(5)

$$Y_{cn} = f(X)$$

$$Y_{ci} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if drought loss} > 0.25 \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where Y_{ci} is a binary variable where losses for crop c due to drought in sub-kebele i are greater than 25%, and it is estimated a non-linear function of all remotely sensed variables of interest X . We present results for damage predictions *here*

2.4.1 Estimation Strategy

2.4.1.1 Random Forests Description

Random forests (RF) are a flexible (used for classification and regression) ensemble learning method that aggregates across multiple classification or regression trees each based on a randomized subset of variables. Each tree is formed through hierarchical splitting method where by each binary split (e.g. NDVI < 0.1) is identified as the most informative, as defined by the greatest reduction in Gini. This ensemble method improves performance by finding the mode or median of ‘weak learners’. This process in turn allows RFs to avoid over-fitting and therefore perform consistently out-of-sample and with noisy data sets.

2.4.1.2 Training vs Testing Data

Before we run any models, we break the data into two groups, with a random selection of 85% of all sub-kebele units being retained for the training and tuning of the models, and 15% of these held aside to provide independent measures of out-of-sample performance.

2.4.1.3 Training Data: Cross Validation & Tuning

To enhance the performance of the models out-of-sample, we undertake two procedures on the training data; tuning and cross validation. Tuning in this case is limited to choosing the number of features (variables) randomly selected for use in each tree. We do a grid search independently for each crop finding the parameter tuning that provides the best performance. To ensure that these parameter tunings work well, we utilize k-fold cross validation whereby the training data is split further into 3 sets of sub-kebele data, the model is trained on two thirds of the data and its performance, using the Kappa coefficient, is estimated using the omitted third sub-sample. Performance for each parameter value is therefore evaluated out-of-sample three times and then averaged. Subsequently, the optimal parameter is that with the highest Kappa value and is specific for each crop model. $\text{Kappa}[\hat{\text{kappa}}]$ is a performance indicator similar to the percentage of observations that are correctly classified but controls for the fact that categories with large numbers of observations are easier to guess by random chance $[\hat{\text{kappa}}]$. $[\hat{\text{kappa}}]$: The Kappa coefficient measures inter-categorical agreement for categorical data. It is generally considered a more robust measure of accuracy, because Kappa takes into account the possibility of the agreement occurring by random chance.

2.4.1.4 Testing Data: Out-Of-Sample Performance

Independent of the training data, we initially withheld 15% of sub-kebele units to provide ‘testing data’ for accurate measures of truly out-of-sample performance for our tuned RF models. These tests should therefore be good indicators of performance for sub-kebeles excluded from the AgSS survey. To test accuracy, we make predictions of the damage category on this testing data and compare them to each locations’ observed damage category. We provide three major performance indicators, a) overall accuracy, 2) Kappa coefficient, and 3) the recall rate⁵. The same metrics are applied to both the national-level (all major growing regions), and the regional-level models (specific to each region).

⁵The percentage of sub-kebeles with ‘substantial drought damage’ that are correctly classified by our models.

3 Results & Discussion

3.1 Spatial Considerations of the 2015 Drought

The 2015 drought had varying spatial impacts on Ethiopia and this section seeks to review how the drought impacted cereal crop production at a variety of spatial scales. We find that impacts generally occurred in local neighborhoods of relatively less productive areas. This creates “pockets” of severely affected areas that has limited impacts on overall national production figures. Figure 5 reveals that only two of the top ten cereal production zones, aggregated by weight, were significantly affected by the drought. More specifically, North Shewa of Amhara and East Shewa of Oromia. Importantly, they are ranked eighth and ninth using this ranking scale. Furthermore, higher impact areas were principally located in the north and northeast of the country. Of critical importance is the fact that while larger administrative areas demonstrated substantial variation of average drought impacts, there was also significant variation at the local level. This is important because many designations of drought areas are determined at the woreda or higher administrative area level. With the high local variance, this suggests that several local areas within the designated drought areas may, in fact, not be experiencing these negative shocks. We suggest a review of this research, with an eye to using smaller level administrative areas, such as the kebele, for possible interventions. Balancing increased logistical considerations (e.g., designating smaller administrative areas as drought affected) with appropriately accurate targeting. In addition, time series trends of damage are fairly consistent across our sample suggesting longer term policy actions in these higher damage areas.

Figure 5: 2015 Local clusters for drought related damages - Wheat

To illustrate the localize nature of drought damages in Ethiopia in 2015, Figure 5 presents the results from a local Getis-Ord test on *drought related* damages for wheat. Results are similar for all other major crops. The “positive” class indicate a significant spatial cluster of high damage values based on a neighborhood of 25km, and “negative” class indicates a significant spatial clustering of low damage values. As you can see, damage clusters center around the eastern stretches of Tigray, the eastern edge of the Simien mountains, and the higher elevation zones of the Ahmar mountains. Notice also that there are small pockets of ‘negative’ clusters, indicating that losses were minimal in these areas. This could be an indication of small regions that have unique micro-climates or were graced by well-timed pockets of rain.

Table 3: Average Cereal Crop Damage by Year (%)

Year	Mean	Standard.Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
2010	11.6	10.9	0	83.2
2011	9.8	9.8	0	76.1
2012	11.6	11.6	0	79.1
2013	8.1	8.1	0	60.5
2014	8.6	8.6	0	94
2015	17.9	17.9	0	95.8

N=1752 for all years

Table 3 depicts average cereal crop loss across the selected sub-kebeles for the six-year period. Overall average rates of cereal crop damage are relatively high for the six years sampled. Typical damage reported was between 8 to 11% per sampled sub-kebele. This suggests that about 10% of all cereal crops are lost due to various damages in a typical crop year. As this is an average across 20 sampled farmers in the sub-kebele this figure does not account for variation within the sample. In other words, individual farmers, or even particular plots, may also experience catastrophic losses while others experience minor damage. Overall, policies aimed to address this “average” form of crop loss should be explored and could go a long way to improving yields and overall production. As expected, the 2015 average crop loss rises dramatically. However, it is important to point out that the 17.9% figure is not evenly applied across equally productive areas and so the total effects on nationally produced cereal crops is different than this figure indicates.

The global Moran’s I depicts relative spatial autocorrelation for the entire area, where positive values convey clustering and negative values convey dispersion.

Figure 6: Indexed Global Morans I Major Cereal Damage 2010-16

While there is some statistically significant global clustering of damage of major cereal crops it is relatively low and demonstrates no observable trend (See Fig. 6). This is an indication that there are some areas of consistent damage but, as demonstrated later, local measures of spatial clustering provide a more nuanced

view. The AgSS allows for about 20 different types of damage (including different types of weather events (hail, floods, and drought), pest, birds and bad seed) but the global clustering of drought impacted cereal crop damage jumped over 7-fold in 2015. The 2011 increase may reflect a drought experienced in this period. Overall, while there is some statistically significant global clustering, it is the 2015 drought that exhibits a relatively dramatic difference.

Figure 7: Drought Effects by Region

Region Codes: 1=Tigray, 3=Amhara, 4=Oromia, 7=SNNP

*Figure 8: Drought Effects by Zone: Tigray Region

Boxplots are presented of the four major regions in Figure 7. What is evident from the figure is that Tigray suffered the most overall damage, has the highest median damage and the widest distribution. The 50% quartiles are more compact, indicating a tighter distribution, moving from northern Tigray to southern SNNP. In addition, the median is skewed far left for all regions suggesting non-normal distributions and large numbers of observations grouping towards zero with outliers of higher damage much farther to the left. For example, approximately 50% of damage values are less than (2%) in both Oromia and SNNPR. Figure 8 splits Tigray region into smaller zonal drought effects. The five zonal distributions are markedly different with median values ranging from 5% to as high as 40%. Both figures suggest wide impacts at both the region and intra-regional level. The following figures (9 & 10) drill down into smaller spatial scales and suggest this variation exists at the intra-zonal level as well.

*Figure 9: Drought Effects by Woreda: Zone 104 *

*Figure 10: Map of Drought Effects by Zone: Tigray Region *

Figure 9 demonstrates that the variability is maintained to exist down to the woreda level. While the data is not as robust, given that the number of observations are fewer at lower administrative levels, values are wide-ranging and indicative of the localized effects of the drought. When placed on a map, the sub-kebeles aggregations, appear to form neighborhoods of similar values that don't necessarily respect administrative boundaries. Broken into 20% categorical damage values, groupings of similar colors seem to present themselves in Figure 10. The 25 kilometer arrow indicates a neighborhood and is placed there for spatial context. The next section provides time-series analysis of group clustering for both hot (above average) and cold (below average drought damage neighborhoods) and investigates statistical patterns related to the drought.

3.1.1 Hotspot Analysis

In order to determine hot and cold spatial damage time trends, Getis-Ord analysis was performed on total damage per crop year using the sub-kebele and its 25-kms radius neighbors as the unit of analysis. This investigation identified local neighborhoods that deviated from the mean value of that year. Individual sub-kebeles were assigned a value of plus one, zero, or minus one if they were in the top 5%, middle 90%, or bottom 5% of neighborhood damage values, respectively for each year. These values were summed for each of the six crop years. For example, a value of -2 indicates that for two crop seasons this particular sub-kebele was in statistically significant low damage neighborhoods. A summation of all values is provided in Table 4.

Table 4: Cold/Hot Damage (per area)

Category	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	Total
0	46.4% (813)	13.6% (239)	7.6% (133)	4.0% (70)	3.5% (62)	1.4% (25)	0.0% (0)	76.6% (1342)
-1	7.9% (139)	1.0% (17)	0.3% (5)	0	0	0		9.2% (161)
-2	5.4% (95)	0% (1)	0	0	0			5.5% (96)
-3	3.0% (53)	0	0	0				3.0% (53)
-4	3.4% (60)	0	0					3.4% (60)
-5	1.3% (23)	0						1.3% (23)
-6	1.0% (17)							1.0% (17)
Total	68.5% (1200)	14.7% (257)	7.9% (138)	4.0% (70)	3.5% (62)	1.4% (25)	0	100% (1752)

Several important issues emerge from the hot/cold spot summation table⁶. Most notably, is the lack of sub-kebeles that had both hot and cold values. More specifically, only 23, or 1.3%, of all sub-kebeles had both positive and negative values. This can be contrasted to 916, or 52%, of sub-kebeles that had either hot or cold values but not both. This suggests that there are certain areas prone to both above and below damage over time. Consistent areas of above and below damage which is explored later.

Table 5: Cold/Hot Damage (per area)

Sub-Kebele Group	Obs	Hot/Cold Spots	Crop Damage	Elevation (m)	NDVI-AOC	PSNP (% of Total)
Control	1459	-0.21	8.80%	1982	225426	30.00%
Drought	293	1.42**	15.5%**	1,855**	162,396**	76.5%**

Access to Extension	Access to Extension (not Tigray)
0.12	-0.06
0.52**	-0.01

⁶All possible values have been inserted into the table and zeros are entered where no value exists but would be theoretically possible. In other words, since there was only six crop seasons included, a value of 5, -2 would not be possible.

** Statistically significant at the 99% level (using relevant normal or non-parametric tests)

The values of Table 5 were divided into base years (2010-2014) and the specific 2015 hot drought year. The base years were averaged to determine “typical values” for each sub-kebele. The goal was to explore predictable patterns for the 2015 drought versus non-drought sub-kebeles. Importantly, many statistically significant differences emerge and suggest that baseline high damage areas were most affected by the drought and suggest a predictability to the impacts.

In total, 293 (16.7%) sub-kebeles experienced statistically significant, above average, neighborhood drought effects. For a variety of variables, statistical differences were found between the drought sub-set and the overall control group. At the very least, this suggests a discernible pattern to the 2015 drought.

The control and drought groups are divided areas that either experienced 2015 neighborhood drought effects or not. The control group represents 1,459 or 83.3% of the entire sample and the remaining are the 2015 drought sub-group. Averages of all variables indicated in Table 5 are taken for 2010-2014 crop seasons and separated by the categorical designation of being in a 2015 drought neighborhood or not. The results are striking and confirm that the drought effects were not randomly distributed. For example, on average the control sub-kebeles experienced 0.2 number of cold spots across all years and essentially suggest no neighborhood effects of damage. On the other hand, each drought affected sub-kebele had an average of 1.4 damage hotspots. This indicates that areas that suffered from the drought, already where in high damage neighborhoods. This is confirmed by the percentage average damage from 2010-14 being about 76% greater on average (15.5% vs. 8.8%) BEFORE the drought year effects. Other variables such as elevation and area of NDVI further suggest significant differences between the groups. The final four columns seek to identify relative policy actions existing in these two groups.

Ethiopia’s Poverty Safety Net Program (PSNP) is an internationally recognized safety net program that provides a variety of social programs to assist poorer households. There are approximately 200 woredas designated as PSNP. For our sample, 660 sub-kebeles or 37.7% are in PSNP designated woredas. However, when separated by drought effects, about 30% are in non-drought areas and an astonishing 76.5% of PSNP samples are in drought neighborhoods. In other words, 3/4 of all drought woredas are in PSNP designated areas, despite the fact that PSNP sub-kebeles make up less than 40% of the entire sample. This suggests this government targeting, via PSNP, is relatively well positioned, at least relative to crop damage effects. Average production losses, over the entire six-year period, in PSNP areas, is 17.9% versus 10.9% in non-PSNP areas. Another potential variable of interest is extension services, and we could hypothesize that extension services are targeted at high production areas. Contrary to this expectation, extension services are disproportionately in drought areas, but this is because the Tigray region experiences disproportionately high extension services. If Tigray is removed, there is no statistical difference.

On the other hand, Agricultural Growth Program (AGP) woredas were selected in 2010 to represent high growth potential areas and are targeted for increased production. As PSNP is social protection and AGP is high production we would expect little overlap of these two groups and actual comparisons confirm this to be the case. In our sample, contrasting the 190 woredas listed as PSNP and 81 listed as AGP, only 6 woredas are listed in both (5 from Tigray and 1 from SNNP). At the sub-kebele level, only 23 of the 1752 observations (1.3%) are listed in both. Unsurprisingly, these AGP woredas have far less damage to crops and suffered less in the 2015 drought. While the AGP sample represents 18.6% of all sampled sub-kebeles (326/1752), 21% of total sub-kebeles were not in high damage neighborhoods in 2015 and only 6.1%, or one-third the overall average, were in hot spots. Further, the non-AGP sub-kebeles had an average of 0.21 hotspots over the 2010-2015 period while the AGP woredas had an average of 0.47 cold spots over the six crop seasons. Finally, in terms of average crop losses over the six crop seasons, AGP sub-kebeles only had an average of 10.8% damage as contrasted to non-AGP value of 14.2%. Overall, Table 5 reveals several statistically significant predictor variables that indicate the relative non-random effects of the drought and 2015 drought impacts in areas of marginal national production.

3.2 Now Casting - Mid-Season OPH Estimates

The following sections outlines our initial efforts into “Now Casting”. We estimate output per hectare using only information available to us from remotely sensed data at mid-season, and the AgSS data collected in the previous year.

Table 6: Now-Casting: Panel RE regression on output per hectare for maize in quintals

Panel RE regression		
=====		
	Dependent variable:	

	MAIZEOPH_W	
	Full	Final
	(1)	(2)

MAIZEOPH_W, 1)	0.2782***	0.2828***
	(0.0142)	(0.0137)
G_mx	0.0031***	0.0029***
	(0.0006)	(0.0005)
G_mx_Qnt	-0.0018***	-0.0018***
	(0.0005)	(0.0005)
G_AUC_leading	-0.00001	
	(0.00001)	
G_height	0.0010***	0.0012***
	(0.0004)	(0.0003)
PET_G_AUC_leading	0.0007***	0.0006***
	(0.0001)	(0.0001)
ETA_G_AUC_leading	-0.0002	
	(0.0005)	
PPT_G_AUC_leading	-0.0017*	-0.0024***
	(0.0009)	(0.0007)
lag(G_height, 1)	0.0001	
	(0.0003)	
lag(season_length, 1)	-0.0494**	-0.0386**
	(0.0204)	(0.0177)
lag(PET_G_mn, 1)	-0.0788***	-0.0732***
	(0.0225)	(0.0210)
lag(PET_G_mx, 1)	0.0208*	0.0243***
	(0.0107)	(0.0081)
lag(PET_G_AUC, 1)	0.0011**	0.0009**
	(0.0005)	(0.0004)
lag(PET_G_sd, 1)	0.0098	
	(0.0175)	
lag(PPT_G_mn, 1)	0.5977***	0.5751***
	(0.2072)	(0.1946)
lag(PPT_G_mx, 1)	0.0100	
	(0.0230)	
lag(PPT_G_AUC, 1)	-0.0100*	-0.0100**
	(0.0051)	(0.0046)
lag(PPT_G_sd, 1)	-0.0644	
	(0.0846)	
lag(MAIZEIMSEED, 1)	0.0093*	0.0179***
	(0.0051)	(0.0039)

lag(MAIZEDAMAGEAREA_P, 1)	-0.6969 (0.7407)	
lag(MAIZEFERT_CHEMICAL_AREA_P, 1)	2.4212*** (0.6323)	2.8591*** (0.6091)
lag(Fert_Amt_Per_Area, 1)	0.0007 (0.0004)	0.0008* (0.0004)
lag(MAIZEEXTAREA, 1)	0.2640** (0.1044)	
lag(MAIZEIMSEED_P, 1)	0.0388** (0.0165)	0.0273* (0.0160)
dist_pp50k	0.000001 (0.00001)	0.000001 (0.00001)
bs(elevation, 3)1	7.9240* (4.4083)	8.1318* (4.4075)
bs(elevation, 3)2	-5.9525* (3.2616)	-6.3998** (3.2556)
bs(elevation, 3)3	2.9830 (6.0532)	3.2109 (6.0528)
Constant	14.8922* (7.9471)	11.2996 (6.8916)

Zone Dummy	Yes	Yes
Observations	5,051	5,051
R2	0.4047	0.4028
Adjusted R2	0.3953	0.3943
F Statistic	42.7821***	47.3026***

Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Looking at the results from Table 6 with regression results from Maize OPH (quintals per hectare) we can see the results from two model outputs. The first, “Full”, presents the results based on the full set of early season variables and includes zonal fixed effects (FE). The second, “Final”, narrows the variable selection.

In Table 6 we can see a decent adjusted R² of 0.39. Residuals are also relatively small with 1st and 3rd quintiles spanning -7.44 and 6.34 quintals per hectare.

Although interpretation is complex for this prediction-oriented model, most variables have the expected sign and significance. First, we can look at contemporaneous variables measured in the current growing season. We can see that increased maximum greenness during the growing season (G_{mx}) corresponds to significantly higher yields ($p < 7.17e-06$). A greater NDVI ‘height’, the difference between growing season minimum and maximum values (G_{height}), corresponds to significantly higher yields ($p < 1.12e-05$). Next variables with the postfix “_leading” indicates that the variable summarizes data between the estimated planting date and maximum NDVI level in the Meher growing season. A higher total potential evapotranspiration⁷ values during ‘leading’ period of the growing season ($PET_G_AUC_leading$) corresponds to higher yields ($p < 1.68e-08$). Interestingly, increased precipitation totals in the leading period of the season ($PPT_G_AUC_leading$) correspond to lower maize yields ($p < 1.68e-08$). This may be an indication that maize is being planted in many areas where excess moisture is problematic. Next, we look at one period lagged variables that give some indication of expected values for any given sub-kebele. The first ($MAIZEOPH_W, 1$) is a one-period lag of maize outputs per hectare, unsurprisingly this variable is both significant and a major determinant ($p < 1.98e-89$). We also see an inverse relationship between last year’s season length and yields ($lag(season_length, 1)$) ($p < 0.0173$), where season length is the difference between estimated planting date and harvest date. This inverse relationship may be related to management practices, where farmers respond to weather or a

⁷Potential evapotranspiration is a measure of evaporative demand. It is the amount of water that could move through a system if water was not a limiting factor and is therefore related to higher temperatures and low humidity.

failing season by trying to either plant early or harvest late. We also see the impact of PET in the previous season higher maximum temperatures and area under the curve (AUC) of PET corresponds to slightly higher yields ($p < 0.00275$). Similarly, a higher mean precipitation last year ($lag(PPT_G_mn, 1)$) corresponds to significantly higher yields ($p < 0.00184$), while higher total precipitation last year corresponds to slightly lower yields ($p < 0.0219$), although this is likely a non-linear response. Both of these coefficients point to the importance and longer-term nature of water availability in soils. In other words, water deficits, at the time of planting, while not recognized in current rainfall data, may impact the current year's yields. We can also look at lagged values of management practices from the AgSS, with lagged improved seed use ($lag(MAIZEIMSEED, 1)$), the percentage ($lag(MAIZEFERT_CHEMICAL_AREA_P, 1)$), and intensity of chemical fertilizers ($lag(Fert_Amt_Per_Area, 1)$) all significantly related to higher yields now ($p < 2.08e-06, p < 5.99e-06, p < 0.0785$, respectively). We can also see the impacts of market access the variable $dist_pp50k$ with increasing distances to population centers of 50k+ people decreasing yields, but is statistically insignificant ($p < 0.97$).

Although R^2 s are reasonably high for real-world data, we believe these models could be significantly improved with the use of 30m harmonized landsat sentinel data. This data should be released in 2018 and will have 5-day coverage. Implying one image is captured every 5-days. This would likely provide a high enough frequency to avoid clouds, and provide reasonable estimates of NDVI curves, but at a much higher resolution (compared to 250m cells used here).

Table 7: Now-Casting: Panel RE regression on output per hectare for wheat in quintals

Panel RE regression

Dependent variable:		

	WHEATOPH_W	
	Full	Final
	(1)	(2)

G_mx	0.0028*** (0.0003)	0.0030*** (0.0002)
G_AUC_leading	-0.00005*** (0.00001)	-0.0001*** (0.00001)
G_height	0.0002 (0.0003)	
PET_G_AUC_leading	0.0008*** (0.0001)	0.0008*** (0.0001)
ETA_G_AUC_leading	0.0002 (0.0004)	
PPT_G_AUC_leading	-0.0009 (0.0007)	
WHEATOPH_W, 1)	0.2559*** (0.0141)	0.2559*** (0.0136)
lag(G_height, 1)	-0.00002 (0.0002)	
lag(season_length, 1)	0.0312** (0.0156)	0.0353*** (0.0112)
lag(PET_G_mn, 1)	-0.0120 (0.0177)	
lag(PET_G_mx, 1)	-0.0144* (0.0086)	-0.0216*** (0.0039)
lag(PET_G_AUC, 1)	0.0001 (0.0004)	
lag(PET_G_sd, 1)	0.0277**	0.0333***

	(0.0141)	(0.0121)
lag(PPT_G_mn, 1)	0.5598***	0.5465***
	(0.1600)	(0.0790)
lag(PPT_G_mx, 1)	0.0200	0.0229***
	(0.0179)	(0.0080)
lag(PPT_G_AUC, 1)	-0.0133***	-0.0134***
	(0.0040)	(0.0022)
lag(PPT_G_sd, 1)	0.0072	
	(0.0662)	
lag(WHEATIMSEED, 1)	0.0019	0.0030***
	(0.0012)	(0.0009)
lag(WHEATDAMAGEAREA_P, 1)	0.1109	
	(0.7415)	
lag(WHEATFERT_CHEMICAL_AREA_P, 1)	1.6010***	1.7386***
	(0.3873)	(0.3747)
lag(Fert_Amt_Per_Area, 1)	0.0005	
	(0.0006)	
lag(WHEATEXTAREA, 1)	0.0082	
	(0.0377)	
lag(WHEATIMSEED_P, 1)	0.0070	
	(0.0048)	
dist_pp50k	-0.00001	
	(0.00001)	
bs(elevation, 3)1	13.9993***	14.2694***
	(3.5715)	(3.5285)
bs(elevation, 3)2	8.8182***	8.8200***
	(1.4739)	(1.4484)
bs(elevation, 3)3	9.7192***	9.8421***
	(2.5937)	(2.5647)
Constant	-22.0545***	-23.7424***
	(7.3098)	(5.9855)

Zone Dummy	Yes	Yes

Observations	5,114	5,115
R2	0.3543	0.3514
Adjusted R2	0.3443	0.3429
F Statistic	35.4135***	41.4393***
=====		

Note: *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

In Table 7 we can see a decent adjusted R^2 of 0.34. Residuals are also relatively small with 1st and 3rd quintiles spanning -5.65 and 4.66 quintals per hectare.

Comparing the results for maize with those here for wheat, we can see interesting differences related to plant physiology, demands, and management. First, we can look at contemporaneous variables measured in the current growing season. Like maize, we can see that increased maximum greenness during the growing season (G_{mx}) corresponds to significantly higher yields ($p < 1.1e-36$), but the sum of NDVI area ($G_{AUC_leading}$) corresponds to slightly lower yields ($p < 1.23e-14$). This may reflect higher yields in areas with a more rapid green up (from minimum to peak greenness). Similarly, we see higher 'leading' period potential evapotranspiration ($PET_G_{AUC_leading}$) increases yields ($p < 2.65e-16$). Looking at lagged variables we can see that again lagged OPH value are a good predictor of the current year ($p < 6.82e-77$). As opposed to maize, longer growing seasons in the previous year ($lag(season_length, 1)$) corresponds to higher yields ($p < 0.00165$). Also opposite of maize, higher evaporative demands (temperatures) in the previous year ($lag(PET_G_{mx}, 1)$) correspond to lower yields ($p < 0.00165$), reflecting reductions in early season water availability through evaporation, as well

as wheat's preference for cooler zones. For precipitation, similar to maize, last years mean ($\text{lag}(PPT_G_mn, 1)$) and maximum precipitation rates ($\text{lag}(PPT_G_max, 1)$) correspond with higher yields ($p < 5.17e-12$, pointing again to the importance of water availability, $p < 5.17e-12$ respectively), while higher previous year total precipitation ($\text{lag}(PPT_G_AUC, 1)$) decreases them ($p < 6.95e-10$). These similarities and differences likely reflect the distinct needs and timing of each crop's ideal growing season characteristics. For AgSS data, we can see that increasing the quantity of improved seeds ($\text{lag}(WHEATIMSEED, 1)$) in the previous year, corresponds to higher yields in this one ($p < 0.00113$). We also see benefits from increasing the percentage covered by chemical fertilizers ($\text{lag}(WHEATFERT_CHEMICAL_AREA_P, 1)$) ($p < 3.58e-06$).

Table 8: Now-Casting: Panel RE regression on output per hectare for barley in quintals

Panel RE regression

	Dependent variable:	
	BARLEYOPH_W	
	Full (1)	Final (2)
G_mx	0.0020*** (0.0002)	0.0018*** (0.0002)
G_AUC_leading	-0.00001 (0.00001)	
G_height	-0.0001 (0.0002)	
PET_G_AUC_leading	0.0004*** (0.0001)	0.0003*** (0.0001)
ETA_G_AUC_leading	0.00002 (0.0003)	
PPT_G_AUC_leading	-0.0021*** (0.0005)	-0.0024*** (0.0004)
BARLEYOPH_W, 1)	0.2512*** (0.0130)	0.2529*** (0.0126)
lag(G_height, 1)	-0.0003** (0.0002)	-0.0003** (0.0001)
lag(season_length, 1)	-0.0172 (0.0122)	
lag(PET_G_mn, 1)	-0.0015 (0.0138)	
lag(PET_G_mx, 1)	-0.0254*** (0.0066)	-0.0222*** (0.0056)
lag(PET_G_AUC, 1)	0.0004 (0.0003)	0.0003*** (0.0001)
lag(PET_G_sd, 1)	0.0267** (0.0107)	0.0254** (0.0104)
lag(PPT_G_mn, 1)	0.3245*** (0.1241)	0.3609*** (0.0814)
lag(PPT_G_mx, 1)	0.0059 (0.0139)	
lag(PPT_G_AUC, 1)	-0.0059* (0.0031)	-0.0070*** (0.0020)
lag(PPT_G_sd, 1)	-0.0298 (0.0504)	
lag(BARLEYIMSEED, 1)	0.00002	

	(0.0022)	
lag(BARLEYDAMAGEAREA_P, 1)	-0.2724	
	(0.5207)	
lag(BARLEYFERT_CHEMICAL_AREA_P, 1)	1.4540***	1.4035***
	(0.3199)	(0.3109)
lag(Fert_Amt_Per_Area, 1)	0.0001	
	(0.0005)	
lag(BARLEYEXTAREA, 1)	0.0113	
	(0.0725)	
lag(BARLEYIMSEED_P, 1)	0.0037	
	(0.0104)	
dist_pp50k	0.000004	
	(0.000004)	
bs(elevation, 3)1	3.0097	2.7110
	(2.1364)	(2.1068)
bs(elevation, 3)2	6.1522***	6.1983***
	(0.9764)	(0.9617)
bs(elevation, 3)3	7.3919***	7.1424***
	(1.5324)	(1.5093)
Constant	3.9554	-1.3144
	(4.8000)	(2.2091)

Zone Dummy	Yes	Yes

Observations	5,854	5,854
R2	0.3721	0.3728
Adjusted R2	0.3637	0.3657
F Statistic	43.8820***	52.9167***
=====		
Note:	*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01	

In Table 8 we can see an adjusted R^2 of 0.37. Residuals are also relatively small with 1st and 3rd quintiles spanning -4.93 and 4.03 quintals per hectare.

Again we can see similarities with other crop models. Like maize, we can see that increased maximum greenness during the growing season (G_{mx}) corresponds to significantly higher yields ($p < 3.9e-24$), but see no impact from other contemporaneous measures of NDVI. Similar to all models, we also see $PET_G_AUC_leading$ increasing yields ($p < 1.62e-07$), and $PPT_G_AUC_leading$ decreasing yields ($p < 4.53e-09$). This would suggest a barley responding positively to early season heat and low levels of precipitation. Lagged PET variables are significant however, with greater PET variability and AUC increasing yields ($p < 0.0132$, $p < 0.00794$ respectively), and declining yields with higher last year maximum PET ($p < 7.16e-05$). Again higher lagged mean precipitation PPT_G_{mn} increases yields, and declining with lagged precipitation AUC ($p < 0.000384$). For AgSS variables, we only see improvements from last years increase in chemical fertilizer coverage ($p < 6.49e-06$).

3.3 Predicting Drought Damages

Here we present results described in the earlier ‘Predicting Crop Losses from Drought’ section in methods. We utilize a random forest to predict losses greater than 25% due to drought using remotely sensed vegetation and weather data, as well as provide measures of test out-of-sample accuracy.

3.3.1 Maize Damages

We can evaluate accuracy with a number of metrics on our independent testing data set described in the “Testing Data: Out-of-sample Performance” section above. Here we compare both in-sample and out-of-sample performance. The first, the confusion matrix compares predicted values against the observed. We also report the a) overall accuracy, 2) Kappa coefficient, and 3) the recall rate as seen in table 9 below:

Table 9: Confusion matrix for reported damages > 0.25% for Maize Out-Of-Sample
FALSE = Crop damages greater than 0.25% for Maize

	FALSE	TRUE
FALSE	41	12
TRUE	30	1205

Table 10: Performance metrics for reported damages > 0.25% for Maize

	Accuracy	Kappa	Recall
Value	0.97	0.64	0.58

Overall, we find a high level of accuracy in our independent *testing* data with overall accuracy of 97 percent. We see reasonable identification of reported maize crop losses with a recall rate of 0.58, indicating that 58% of all substantial loss cases were predicted. In all, 41 out of 71 reported cases were predicted, and 12 cases were falsely predicted as crop failure areas. Although the recall rate is relatively low, we can still say that we can identify healthy maize harvest 1205 out of 1217 times, or 99% of the time. Clearly, additional work is needed to better identify the high damage, low probability events. However, the importance of this research should not be understated, early identification of localized crop failure could be useful for policy action, and adoption of the more accurate 30m HLS data could radically improve results.

We can also examine the relative importance of each variable to the national-level model, as well as its estimated non-linear relationship with the dependent variable through partial dependency plots. First, let’s examine the relative importance of each variable in the random forest through the role it played in Gini coefficient loss.

Figure 11: Top 10 variable importance plot for maize damage prediction

From the figure above, we can see that the most important variables are comprised of measures of changes in NDVI (G_Qnt_diff, A_Qnt_diff, G_max_diff) as well as measures of change (PPT_G_mn_diff, PPT_G_AUC_diff_mn), mean (PPT_G_mn), 90th percentile values (PPT_G_Qnt) and standard deviation (PPT_G_sd) in precipitation. Changes in total potential evapotranspiration over the growing season, a measure of evaporative demand (largely controlled by temperature and humidity), also plays a key role (PET_G_AUC_diff_mn, PET_G_AUC_diff_90th). We can see that the most important variables for maize are largely comprised of measures of change in the mean and upper level of the distribution of greenness, precipitation, and potential evapotranspiration. This points to one of the advantages of machine learning, since these algorithms can exploit even minor difference between otherwise colinear variables in order to provide a reliable model fit.

G_Qnt_diff has the highest relative importance in the random forest model. G_Qnt_diff is measured as the first difference in the 90th percentile NDVI value for the growing season. As such, the change in the highest NDVI values reflects a measure of change in plant health, with positive G_Qnt_diff values corresponding to increased plant health relative to the previous growing season. We can also see that the most important variables are largely comprised of variables summarizing NDVI, with the exception of PPT_G_mn which is the mean value of precipitation for each 10 day period across the growing season, and PPT_G_AUC_Qnt, the 90th percentile of the area under the curve values for precipitation. Each one of these variables will have a specific non-linear response, with curves being estimated by actual plant, weather, and farmer behavior observed remotely or through the AgSS.

We can now look at the partial dependence plots⁸ to help understand the non-linear response of reported damages to variables of interest, such as G_Qnt_diff. On the Y axis, note that higher values indicate a greater likelihood of substantial crop losses.

⁸These plots are graphical visualizations of the marginal effect of a given variable (or multiple variables) on an outcome.

Figure 12: Partial dependency plot for influence of G_Qnt_diff on maize damage prediction

In the figure above, we can see how the likelihood of reporting maize losses decreases rapidly as the first difference of G_Qnt (G_Qnt_diff) approaches zero. G_Qnt , itself, measures the 90th percentile of NDVI values over the Meher growing season. Negative values of the first difference therefore indicates the current year's 90th percentile NDVI is lower than the previous, and positive values, higher than the last year. Therefore G_Qnt_diff picks up on the changes in peak values of NDVI. As expected, the likelihood of loss is highest with large negative first differences. This likelihood declines rapidly as it approaches zero, reaching a minima between 0 and 100. Then the likelihood of losses ticks up slightly as even higher values are observed. This is likely related to farm management issues, such as the failure to remove weeds (that would increase NDVI values past that normally expected). Additionally, the uptick might also be relate to only a small number of observations past 100. Similarly, we can look at the partial dependence plot for other variables of interest such as $PPT_G_mn_diff$.

Figure 13: Partial dependency plot for influence of PPT_G_mn_diff on maize damage prediction

PPT_G_mn_diff tracks the effects of the change in average 10-day precipitation across the growing season. We can see that year-over-year declines (negative numbers) correspond to a much higher likelihood of crop losses due to drought. The likelihood of failure declines rapidly around a value of -10mm, and reaches its lowest likelihood just above 0mm. Past this, we again see an increase the likelihood of damage, but at a slower rate. Finally, years with extremely large increases in precipitation also correspond to increased damage due to excess precipitation or damaging storms, although this is likely driven by few observations.

We can see how average precipitation corresponds to drought related crop failures with variables such as PPT_G_mn.

Figure 14: Partial dependency plot for influence of PPT_G_mn on maize damage prediction

Similarly, we can see how the average 10-day precipitation effects the likelihood of loss. Losses decline rapidly above a 20mm 10-day average, reaching a minima around 40mm, but then increasing again after 60mm. Interestingly, the large uptick in reported losses due to drought at high levels of precipitation is unexpected. This may have to do with issues of farmers confusing general weather related losses (excess rain) with drought related losses, as well as a very small number of observations greater than 60mm. From a policy perspective, this difference is likely trivial since interventions should target losses more generally.

3.3.2 Wheat Damages

The confusion matrix compares predicted values against the observed (reference). We also report the a) overall accuracy, 2) Kappa coefficient, and 3) the recall rate as seen in table 11 below:

Table 11: Confusion matrix for reported damages > 0.25% for Wheat
 FALSE = Crop damages greater than 0.25% for Wheat

	FALSE	TRUE
FALSE	18	3
TRUE	17	856

Table 12: Performance metrics for reported damages > 0.25% for Wheat

	Accuracy	Kappa	Recall
Value	0.98	0.63	0.51

Overall, we find a high level of accuracy in our completely independent *testing* data with overall accuracy of 98 percent. For the case of wheat, we see a lower identification of reported wheat crop losses with a recall rate of 0.51, indicating that 51% of all substantial loss cases were correctly predicted. In all, 18 out of 35 reported cases were predicted, and 3 cases were falsely predicted as crop failure areas. Although the recall rate is relatively low, we can still say that we can identify healthy maize harvest 856 out of 859 times, or 99.7% of the time.

We can also examine the relative importance of each variable to the national-level model, as well as its estimated non-linear relationship with the dependent variable through partial dependency plots. First, let's examine the relative importance of each variable in the random forest through the role it played in Gini coefficient loss.

Figure 15: Top 10 variable importance plot for wheat damage prediction

From the figure above, we see a similar set of variables relative to maize, while the order and level of importance has changed. Importantly, G_Qnt_diff remains the most important variable and suggests a robustness of this particular variable. This is an indication that our models are able to utilize the same broad set of phenological and weather variables to identify differences between crop types and how their losses can be observed.

We can see that G_Qnt_diff has the highest relative importance in the random forest model. G_Qnt_diff is the first difference of G_Qnt (G_Qnt_diff), where G_Qnt is the 90th percentile of NDVI values in the Meher season. As such, the high NDVI values reflect a measure of plant health, with higher G_Qnt_diff values corresponding to strong plant health (higher leaf area, low water stress) at some point in the growing season. We can also see that the most important variables are largely comprised of variables summarizing NDVI, with the exception of PPT_G_mn which is the mean value of precipitation for each 10 day period across the growing season.

Interestingly, comparing figures 15 and 11, we see that measures of potential evapotranspiration (temperature and humidity) play a smaller role in losses for wheat compared to maize. This might reflect physiological differences between plants, where variability in temperatures more greatly effects yields for Maize. The differences between models validates our suite of variables as well as the need to run plant specific models.

We can now look at the partial dependence plots to help understand the non-linear response of reported drought damages to G_Qnt_diff.

Figure 16: Partial dependency plot for influence of *G_Qnt_diff* on wheat damage prediction

In the figure above, we can see with *G_Qnt_diff*, similar to maize, how the likelihood of reporting maize losses decreases rapidly after -500, with a minima above zero. The likelihood of losses again increases at the upper end of the distribution. These losses at upper end of the distribution might reflect poor management such as failure to control weeds, or narrow row spacing. The consistency across independent crop models (maize and wheat) is a strong indication that these models are picking up on meaningful non-linear relations. Similarly, we can look at the partial dependence plot for other variables of interest such as *PPT_G_mn_diff*.

Figure 17: Partial dependency plot for influence of PPT_G_mn_diff on wheat damage prediction

Looking again at Figure 17, we can see similarities and differences between the likelihood of losses for wheat compared to maize. For wheat, we see that the likelihood of losses at very negative levels of PPT_G_mn_diff is both higher (note differences in the y-axis intercept values: -3 for maize vs -2.25 for wheat), and declines more slowly as the change in average precipitation increases. They both however hit a minima above 0. However wheat losses do not increase again, at all, until extremely high increases in precipitation year-over-year (above +15mm). Now we can look at the partial dependence plot for other variables of interest such as PET_A_mn.

Figure 18: Partial dependency plot for influence of PET_A_mn on wheat damage prediction

In the figure above, we can see the relationship between average annual potential evapotranspiration (PET_A_mn) and drought related losses. As expected, losses are flat/stable until extremely high levels of PET, indicating high temperatures and low humidity. This relationship validates our models by picking up on the expected relationship between potential evapotranspiration and drought damage. This plot also confirms the critical importance of non-linear relationships not easily captured in regression approaches.

3.3.3 Sorghum Damages

The confusion matrix compares predicted values against the observed (reference). We also report the a) overall accuracy, 2) Kappa coefficient, and 3) the recall rate as seen in table 13 below:

Table 13: Confusion matrix for reported damages $> 0.25\%$ for Sorghum
 FALSE = Crop damages greater than 0.25% for Sorghum

	FALSE	TRUE
FALSE	32	9
TRUE	18	904

Table 14: Performance metrics for reported damages $> 0.25\%$ for Sorghum

	Accuracy	Kappa	Recall
Value	0.97	0.69	0.64

Overall, we find a high level of accuracy in our completely independent *testing* data with overall accuracy of 97

percent. For the case of Sorghum, we see a decent identification of reported Sorghum crop losses with a recall rate of 0.64, indicating that 64% of all substantial loss cases were predicted in our completely independent *testing* data. In all, 32 out of 50 reported cases were predicted, and 9 cases were falsely predicted as crop failure areas. Although the recall rate is relatively low, we can still say that we can identify healthy maize harvest 904 out of 913 times, or 99% of the time.

3.3.4 Barley Damages

The confusion matrix compares predicted values against the observed (reference). We also report the a) overall accuracy, 2) Kappa coefficient, and 3) the recall rate as seen in table 15 below:

Table 15: Confusion matrix for reported damages > 0.25% for barley
FALSE = Crop damages greater than 0.25% for barley

	FALSE	TRUE
FALSE	28	7
TRUE	23	872

Table 16: Performance metrics for reported damages > 0.25% for barley

	Accuracy	Kappa	Recall
Value	0.97	0.63	0.55

Overall, we find a high level of accuracy in our completely independent *testing* data with overall accuracy of 97 percent. For the case of barley, we see a reasonable identification of reported losses with a recall rate of only 0.55, indicating that 55% of all substantial loss cases were predicted in our independent *testing* data. In all, 28 out of 51 reported cases were predicted, and 7 cases were falsely predicted as crop failure areas. Although the recall rate is relatively low, we can still say that we can identify healthy maize harvest 872 out of 879 times, or 99% of the time.

3.3.5 Teff Damages

The confusion matrix compares predicted values against the observed (reference). We also report the a) overall accuracy, 2) Kappa coefficient, and 3) the recall rate as seen in table 17 below:

Table 17: Confusion matrix for reported damages > 0.25% for teff
FALSE = Crop damages greater than 0.25% for teff

	FALSE	TRUE
FALSE	26	2
TRUE	26	1094

Table 18: Performance metrics for reported damages > 0.25% for teff

	Accuracy	Kappa	Recall
Value	0.98	0.64	0.5

Overall, we find a high level of accuracy in our completely independent *testing* data with overall accuracy of 98 percent. For the case of teff, we see relatively good identification of reported losses with a recall rate of only 0.5, indicating that 50% of all substantial loss cases were predicted in our independent *testing* data. In all, 26 out of 52 reported cases were predicted, and 2 cases were falsely predicted as crop failure areas. Although the recall rate is relatively low, we can still say that we can identify healthy maize harvest 1094 out of 1096 times, or 100% of the time.

3.4 Predict Damages Out-Of-Sample

One possible use case of these models is to predict losses outside of AgSS sample areas or before AgSS data is released. This will allow policy makers to identify potential at-risk communities rapidly at low cost. Given the importance of maximum and 90th percentile values of NDVI in model performance, a reasonable estimate could be made mid-season (or just past peak greenness) similar to the approach in ‘Now Casting’. As example of how this might work we extracted NDVI statistics for all 75k+ sub-kebeles and used the model trained on AgSS sample areas for 2016, without access to AgSS data for that year.

Figure 19: Count of Predicted Damages (>25%) at the Sub-Kebele Level for 2016

In this particular example, we provide an estimate of the total number of drought related losses (for all crops) for remotely sensed observations of the 2016 growing season. Although 2016 generally saw above average precipitation rates (see Figure 1C) it is still possible to identify localized pockets of drought. As you can see, this model was able to identify isolated clusters of at-risk communities that experienced substantial losses in 2016 despite generally favorable weather. These losses are likely due to the effects of Ethiopia’s complex terrain which shapes it’s patterns of rainfall. Additionally, if using the “Now-Casting” approach, this type of prediction could be provided midway through the growing season, acting as a method for rapid assessment, to help target food aid or agricultural extension.

4 Conclusions

This paper covers a wide variety of statistical and econometric models that seek to provide an empirical understanding of droughts. Our unique data set covering six crop seasons and ending with the 2015 drought, includes GIS, survey and remote sensing variables. At the national level, for NDVI alone, we processed 21,664,250,880 pixels. A scale which required us to utilize cutting-edge parallel processing made available to us for free by The George Washington University. After the time series were summarized, approximately 1,752 sub-kebeles were sampled for a total of about 10,500 total observations. We began by using both global and local forms of spatial clustering to review damage hot and cold spots in Ethiopia. Results indicated that higher damage areas were those most likely to be affected by drought. This was reflected by policy whereby areas previously designated for social protection (PSNP) were those most likely to be in hot spots. However, it is unclear if this type of information has been made aware to policymakers. Using both lagged household survey data and current remote sensing information, preliminary models were developed for mid-crop cycle productivity estimation. The goal is to develop earlier, and more accurate, predictions of cereal crop productivity. This type of “Now Casting” could supplement current early warning systems that have not fared as well recently. Finally, random forest models were developed to explain high crop loss areas. Here we are able to identify areas with greater than 25% losses, completely out of sample, very accurately. We see room for improvement through recent advances in automated feature extraction (to summarize variability in NDVI, PPT, and PET), as well as deep learning models that can now be easily applied to these data through Google’s recent open-source release of the TensorFlow algorithms.

Considering the complexity of the task, results were extremely encouraging. We provide evidence that our models pick up on meaningful non-linear relationships expected from differences in crops including differences in phenology, and responses to temperatures and precipitation. With more development, models like these could be used to provide accurate first-order estimates of both crop yield by type, and help identify those areas with significant agricultural losses. Moreover, these predictions could be made in the first half of the growing season, providing a critical opportunity for early nation and local intervention. We believe efforts such as these can expand upon the current famine early warning systems, and field-based rapid assessments. Eventually with a longer period of training data, and higher resolution input data, the AgSS might be largely or completely replaced by this type of remote assessment.

Although R^2 s and predictive accuracy are reasonably high for real-world data, we believe these models could be significantly improved with the use of 30m harmonized landsat sentinel (HLS) data. This data should be released in 2018 and will have 5-day coverage. Implying one image is captured every 5-days. This would likely provide a high enough frequency to avoid clouds, and provide reasonable estimates of NDVI curves, but at a much higher resolution (compared to 250m cells used here). We believe this will be critical to improve on our results going forward, as it will allow us to better distinguish between agricultural and non-agricultural cells, avoiding cells that are a mixture of crops and forest. The methods developed through this study, and previous ones, have been specifically designed to transfer to the new HLS data stream, thus greatly improving our model accuracy, while minimizing further development time. Furthermore, even higher resolution data (<1 meter) available every day, like that from Planet Labs, could allow IFPRI to explore farmer behavior from sampled farms including everything from row spacing, water management practices, technology adoption, and tilling methods (for instance no-till vs conventional).

5 Appendix

5.1 Methods - Exploratory Analysis of Output Per Hectare Regression

5.1.1 Estimation Strategy

5.1.1.1 Variable Selection

One of the key challenges is how to decide on which of the 126 variables from AgSS and MODIS we want to include in the model. For this task we relied on a new suite of variable selection tools coming out of the computer science domain. We utilized VSURF that utilizes a two-stage strategy based on preliminary ranking of all explanatory variables for prediction using the random forests permutation-based score of importance, and finalized with a forward step-wise strategy for variable introduction.

Here we utilize VSURF to select unique sets of variables for each crop (barley, maize, wheat, teff). Given the complexity of these permutations for each crop (100s of millions) we utilize 15 cores of the GWU supercomputer Colonial One. Each run took between 10-24 hours.

5.1.1.2 Panel Regression

Compared to cross-sectional approaches, panel analysis can substantially increase the degree of observed variance over both space and time. For instance, in our current application, the integration of sub-kebeles (with $n = 1752$) over the 2010-2015 sample period ($t = 6$), results in a substantially larger data ($N \sim 6900$), allowing for a much greater flexibility and degrees of freedom in the modelling of the issue of interest. Here we include a few variables of interest to the reader including Zonal and annual dummies, and a lagged value of output per hectare. Here we estimate a series of random effect models of the following form 6:

(6)

$$Y_{itc} = \alpha_i + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k X_{it} + \mu_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

where Y_{itc} is the output per hectare (OPH) for crop c for sub-kebele i for year t , α is the average output per hectare for sample population (country), $\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k X_{it}$ is the sum of all K coefficient estimates β_k for all variables X , μ_i is the sub-kebele specific random effect that measures the difference between the average OPH at sub-kebele i and the average OPH in the entire country. The term ϵ_{it} is the individual-specific effect, which can be described as the deviation of the i th OPH from the average for that year.

Here we present preliminary results from panel regressions on output per hectare for Ethiopia's major crops. These variables reflect the initial selection from the VSURF algorithm.

5.2 Results - Exploratory Analysis of Output Per Hectare Regression

Here we present results from panel regressions as outlined in the "Estimating Crop Yields" section. The dependent variable is crop yields (output per hectare) measured in quintals (1 quintal = 100 kilograms). The independent variables are initial selected using the VSURF algorithm described in the methods section. Here we present the findings of three major crops: maize, wheat, and barley. The remainder are presented in the appendix at the end of this document

Table 19: Panel RE regression on output per hectare for maize in quintals

Panel RE regression

	Dependent variable:			
	MAIZEOPH_W			
	Full (1)	Reduced (2)	Final (3)	No AgSS (4)
MAIZEOPH_W, 1)	0.3262*** (0.0101)	0.3227*** (0.0101)	0.3265*** (0.0100)	0.3653*** (0.0103)
G_mn	0.0029** (0.0014)	0.0021 (0.0013)	0.0025* (0.0013)	0.0029** (0.0013)
G_AUC_leading	0.000004 (0.000004)			
G_AUC_Qnt	0.000003 (0.00002)			
A_mn	-0.0053*** (0.0017)	-0.0045*** (0.0016)	-0.0034*** (0.0012)	-0.0049*** (0.0013)
A_max	-0.00003 (0.0005)			
A_AUC	0.0000* (0.0000)	0.0000 (0.0000)		
A_Qnt	0.0018*** (0.0006)	0.0020*** (0.0005)	0.0027*** (0.0004)	0.0048*** (0.0004)
A_AUC_Qnt	-0.0000 (0.0000)			
A_max_Qnt	-0.0010** (0.0004)	-0.0010*** (0.0004)	-0.0007** (0.0003)	-0.0014*** (0.0003)
T_G_Qnt	0.0013* (0.0007)	0.0012* (0.0006)		
PPT_A_max	0.0010 (0.0083)	0.0001 (0.0078)		
PPT_G_AUC_Qnt	0.0020** (0.0010)	0.0023*** (0.0007)	0.0024*** (0.0007)	0.0027*** (0.0007)
PPT_G_mx_Qnt	-0.0204** (0.0094)	-0.0183** (0.0089)	-0.0189** (0.0083)	-0.0309*** (0.0086)
PPT_T_G_Qnt	0.0201 (0.0222)			
PET_A_min	0.0108*** (0.0032)	0.0125*** (0.0032)	0.0118*** (0.0031)	0.0169*** (0.0032)
PET_G_AUC_diff_mn	0.0006*** (0.0001)	0.0005*** (0.0001)	0.0006*** (0.0001)	0.0003** (0.0001)
MAIZEAREA	0.1171*** (0.0440)	0.0545 (0.0432)		
MAIZESEED1AREA	-0.0195 (0.1486)			
Fert_Amt_Per_Area		0.0015*** (0.0004)	0.0015*** (0.0004)	
MAIZEIMSEED	0.0216*** (0.0047)	0.0186*** (0.0031)	0.0191*** (0.0031)	
MAIZEDAMAGEAREA_P	-11.1709***	-11.1543***	-11.0321***	

	(0.5803)	(0.5715)	(0.5673)	
MAIZEFERT_CHEMICAL_AREA	-0.2302**			
	(0.0970)			
MAIZEFERT_CHEMICAL_AMT	0.0002			
	(0.0001)			
MAIZEEXTAREA	0.2161**	0.1061	0.1513**	
	(0.0936)	(0.0766)	(0.0668)	
Y_COORD	-0.000001	0.000001		
	(0.000003)	(0.000003)		
X_COORD	0.00001***	0.00001***	0.00001***	0.000004
	(0.000003)	(0.000003)	(0.000003)	(0.000003)
elevation	-0.0019***			
	(0.0003)			
splines::bs(elevation, 3)1		15.4945***	15.5929***	23.8067***
		(3.8604)	(3.7878)	(3.9425)
splines::bs(elevation, 3)2		4.6195***	4.5506***	7.7403***
		(1.5420)	(1.5263)	(1.5913)
splines::bs(elevation, 3)3		4.3731	4.3404*	8.6528***
		(2.6649)	(2.6305)	(2.7460)
c(Year)	0.7367***	0.7053***	0.6262***	0.5059***
	(0.1042)	(0.1031)	(0.0813)	(0.0838)
Constant	2.0693	-9.9053*	-7.2621**	-17.1149***
	(5.0900)	(5.5259)	(2.9705)	(3.0796)

Zone Dummy	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	8,241	8,241	8,241	8,241
R2	0.4630	0.4675	0.4696	0.4211
Adjusted R2	0.4576	0.4624	0.4648	0.4163
F Statistic	84.7407***	91.8726***	99.0421***	86.1521***

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Looking at the results from Table 19 with regression results from Maize OPH (quintals per hectare) we can see the results from four model outputs. The first, “Full”, presents the results based on the model selection from the VSURF algorithm and includes zonal fixed effects (FE). The second, “Reduced”, narrows the variable selection while including critical non-linearity for variables such as elevation, and adds a variable *Fert_Amt_Per_Area* which is the amount of chemical fertilizer applied per unit area. Non-linearity is controlled for using basis-splines which outperform polynomial representations in terms of stability and forecasting. The third model, “Final”, represents the final selection of significant variables for estimation. The last model, “No AgSS”, omits all AgSS survey variables to demonstrate the ability of the model to predict yields on the basis of remotely sensed data and last years yields.

Looking at the final model we can see an impressive adjusted R² of 0.46. Residuals are also relatively small with 1st and 3rd quintiles spanning -7.66 and 6.56 quintals. These findings are relatively impressive considering the highly-localized nature of these estimates (at the sub-kebele level), and the relatively coarse spatial resolution of the remotely sensed data (250m). Looking more closely we can observe some important features.

First, remotely sensed variables, while complex, have a few tangible interpretations. For instance, *G_mn* is positive and significant (p<0.0503) indicating that yields are higher if the mean greenness (NDVI) level during the Meher growing season is higher. Similarly, increases in the 90th percentile of greenness for the entire year (*A_Qnt*), corresponds to statistically significant higher yields (p<1.66e-12). Interestingly, the variable *A_mn*, which is the mean greenness level (NDVI) for the entire year, is negative and significant (p<0.00498). Already controlling for conditions during the Meher season, this might be an indication of two

issues, a) a higher A_{mn} might indicate the failure to properly till or remove weeds between seasons, or b) complications of management in dual-crop areas, where planting occurs for both the minor (Belg) and major (Meher) rainy season.

Looking at precipitation variables we can see that $PPT_G_AUC_Qnt$ yields are higher ($p < 0.000716$) in sub-kebeles where the 90th percentile of total rainfall during the Meher season is higher. The opposite is true ($p < 0.0223$) for areas with higher 90 percentile maximum rainfalls ($PPT_G_mx_Qnt$) likely reflecting the impact of flooding or excess rain events. Additionally, areas with higher minimum potential evaporation rates (PET_A_min : higher min temps, more sun) receive better yields ($p < 0.000137$) while controlling for precipitation and greenness, and areas with above average total PET ($PET_G_AUC_diff_mn$) also receive yield benefits ($p < 7.83e-06$).

The AgSS data also provide some insights. We see scant evidence for yield improvements based on planted area alone ($MAIZEAREA$ $p < 0.207$), but we do see the positive effects of fertilization rates ($Fert_Amt_Per_Area$ $p < 0.000357$), the use of improved seeds ($MAIZEIMSEED$ $p < 6.31e-10$), and the area of land in the sub-kebele that has utilized extension agents ($MAIZEEXTAREA$ $p < 0.0234$). Conversely, we see the substantial impact of the percent of reported crop damage ($MAIZEDAMAGEAREA_P$), with every additional one percent of land damaged corresponding to a -11 unit loss in OPH ($p < 2.21e-82$).

Table 20: Panel RE regression on output per hectare for wheat in quintals

Panel RE regression

	Dependent variable:			
	WHEATOPH_W			
	Full (1)	Reduced (2)	Final (3)	No AgSS (4)
WHEATOPH_W, 1)	0.2819*** (0.0123)	0.2786*** (0.0123)	0.2800*** (0.0123)	0.2995*** (0.0124)
G_mx	0.0011*** (0.0004)	0.0012*** (0.0004)	0.0012*** (0.0004)	0.0027*** (0.0004)
A_max_Qnt	-0.0010** (0.0004)	-0.0011*** (0.0004)	-0.0011*** (0.0004)	-0.0014*** (0.0004)
T_G_Qnt	0.0014*** (0.0005)	0.0014*** (0.0005)	0.0015*** (0.0005)	0.0007 (0.0005)
PPT_G_Qnt	-0.0486* (0.0278)	-0.0504* (0.0277)	-0.0514* (0.0277)	-0.0385 (0.0284)
PPT_G_sd	0.2000*** (0.0761)	0.2064*** (0.0760)	0.2084*** (0.0759)	0.1924** (0.0780)
PPT_T_G_Qnt	-0.0851*** (0.0157)	-0.0881*** (0.0155)	-0.0874*** (0.0154)	-0.0935*** (0.0158)
PET_G_mn	0.0073** (0.0037)	0.0071* (0.0037)	0.0074** (0.0037)	0.0040 (0.0038)
PET_G_sd	-0.0378*** (0.0105)	-0.0387*** (0.0105)	-0.0388*** (0.0104)	-0.0430*** (0.0107)
WHEATAREA	0.0524 (0.0731)	-0.0185 (0.0630)	0.0830*** (0.0292)	
WHEATNIMSEED	0.0005* (0.0003)	0.0004 (0.0003)		
WHEATNIMSEED_P	0.0008 (0.0008)			
WHEATDAMAGEAREA_P	-9.9877*** (0.6623)	-9.8762*** (0.6606)	-9.8837*** (0.6607)	
Fert_Amt_Per_Area		-0.0013 (0.0008)		
WHEATFERT_CHEMICAL_AMT	0.0007*** (0.0002)	0.0009*** (0.0003)	0.0006*** (0.0002)	
WHEATFERT_CHEMICAL_AREA	-0.0701 (0.0726)			
WHEATFERT_CHEMICAL_AREA_P	1.8323*** (0.3831)	1.3742*** (0.3406)	1.4219*** (0.3365)	
X_COORD	0.00001** (0.000003)	0.00001** (0.000003)	0.00001** (0.000003)	0.00001 (0.000004)
Y_COORD	0.000003 (0.000003)	0.000001 (0.000003)		
dist_rcap	0.000003 (0.000004)			
elevation	0.0017*** (0.0003)			
bs(elevation, 3)1		9.2350***	9.5196***	13.2382***

		(2.4118)	(2.3844)	(2.4551)
bs(elevation, 3)2		5.6638***	5.4246***	9.1046***
		(1.2403)	(1.2319)	(1.2223)
bs(elevation, 3)3		7.2098***	7.4203***	8.9010***
		(1.9324)	(1.9158)	(1.9799)
c(Year)	1.0661***	1.0796***	1.0799***	1.0858***
	(0.0934)	(0.0931)	(0.0930)	(0.0948)
Constant	-9.0136	-7.0887	-6.4993	-10.3012**
	(6.7203)	(6.7159)	(4.6303)	(4.7753)

Zone Dummy	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Observations	5,660	5,660	5,660	5,660
R2	0.4039	0.4059	0.4064	0.3671
Adjusted R2	0.3962	0.3983	0.3990	0.3597
F Statistic	52.5652***	53.0250***	55.4557***	49.9115***
=====				

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Looking at the results from Table 20 with regression results from Wheat OPH (quintals per hectare) we can see the results from four model outputs. The first, “Full”, presents the results based on the model selection from the VSURF algorithm and includes zonal fixed effects (FE). The second, “Reduced”, narrows the variable selection while including critical non-linearity for variables such as elevation, and adds key variables. The third model, “Final”, represents the final selection of significant variables for estimation. The last model, “No AgSS”, omits all AgSS survey variables to demonstrate the ability of the model to predict yields on the basis of remotely sensed data and last years yields.

In Table 20 we can see an impressive adjusted R² of 0.4. Residuals are also relatively small with 1st and 3rd quintiles spanning -5.64 and 4.62 quintals per hectare. Although interpretation is complex for this prediction-oriented model, most variables have the expected sign and significance. Increased maximum greenness during the growing season G_{max} corresponds to significantly higher yields ($p < 0.00269$). Interestingly, most measures of precipitation like $PPT_{G_{Qnt}}$ (while controlling for greenness, a proxy of plant health) corresponds to lower yields, perhaps indicating that most wheat growing areas have suffered from excess rain during the sample period ($p < 0.0634$). While higher mean evaporative demand $PET_{G_{mn}}$ (related to higher temperatures and lower humidity) correspond to higher yields ($p < 0.0431$). Like maize $A_{max_{Qnt}}$ has the opposite sign perhaps for similar reason (poor management).

Looking at AgSS survey data we can see that improved seeds $WHEATNIMSEED$ have a positive and nearly statistically significant effect ($p < 0.0537$). Both the amount $WHEATFERT_{CHEMICAL_AMT}$ and percentage covered $WHEATFERT_{CHEMICAL_AREA_P}$ by chemical fertilizers had large statistically significant effects ($p < 0.000301$, $p < 2.42e-05$ respectively). Although unstable, we also see the possibility of gains from scale with area planted $WHEATAREA$ having a small significant effect in the final model ($p < 2.42e-05$).

Table 21: Panel RE regression on output per hectare for barley in quintals

Panel RE regression

	Dependent variable:			
	BARLEYOPH_W			
	Full (1)	Reduced (2)	Final (3)	No AgSS (4)
BARLEYOPH_W, 1)	0.2247*** (0.0122)	0.2273*** (0.0121)	0.2272*** (0.0121)	0.2420*** (0.0124)
G_mx	0.0007* (0.0004)	0.0007* (0.0004)	0.0007* (0.0004)	0.0010*** (0.0004)
G_Qnt	0.0020*** (0.0004)	0.0019*** (0.0004)	0.0019*** (0.0004)	0.0026*** (0.0004)
A_AUC_Qnt	-0.0000 (0.0000)			
A_max_Qnt	-0.0015*** (0.0003)	-0.0015*** (0.0003)	-0.0015*** (0.0003)	-0.0020*** (0.0003)
PPT_A_max	-0.0008 (0.0140)			
PPT_G_AUC	-0.0038 (0.0024)			
PPT_A_mn	0.1328 (0.0930)			
PPT_G_sd	-0.2603* (0.1413)	-0.0838 (0.1006)		
PPT_A_sd	0.3365** (0.1570)	0.1225 (0.1022)	0.0393** (0.0200)	0.0502** (0.0204)
PPT_G_AUC_leading	-0.0005 (0.0004)			
PPT_G_AUC_Qnt	0.0028*** (0.0010)	0.0022** (0.0008)	0.0022*** (0.0008)	0.0015* (0.0008)
PPT_G_mx_Qnt	-0.0228*** (0.0078)	-0.0168** (0.0075)	-0.0166** (0.0075)	-0.0188** (0.0075)
PPT_T_G_Qnt	-0.0717*** (0.0199)	-0.0704*** (0.0193)	-0.0723*** (0.0191)	-0.0651*** (0.0193)
PET_G_mx	0.0009 (0.0023)	0.0007 (0.0022)		
BARLEYFERT_CHEMICAL_AMT	0.0003 (0.0004)			
Fert_Amt_Per_Area		0.00003 (0.0006)		
BARLEYDAMAGEAREA_P	-7.4954*** (0.4995)	-7.4406*** (0.4959)	-7.4451*** (0.4953)	
BARLEYFERT_CHEMICAL_AREA	0.2160*** (0.0638)	0.2336*** (0.0505)	0.2330*** (0.0503)	
BARLEYFERT_NATURAL_AREA	-0.0454 (0.1131)			
Y_COORD	-0.000004 (0.000003)	-0.000004 (0.000003)	-0.000004 (0.000003)	-0.00001* (0.000003)
X_COORD	0.00001***	0.00001***	0.00001***	0.00001***

	(0.000003)	(0.000003)	(0.000003)	(0.000003)
dist_rcap	0.000004			
	(0.000003)			
elevation	0.0030***			
	(0.0003)			
bs(elevation, 3)1		1.7332	1.6812	2.2073
		(2.0808)	(2.0792)	(2.0972)
bs(elevation, 3)2		6.1018***	6.1017***	7.7045***
		(0.9744)	(0.9717)	(0.9733)
bs(elevation, 3)3		6.2416***	6.1964***	7.8908***
		(1.5140)	(1.5080)	(1.5236)
c(Year)	0.5863***	0.6669***	0.6811***	0.6120***
	(0.0830)	(0.0660)	(0.0638)	(0.0652)
Constant	2.5650	6.2490	6.2445	4.4223
	(4.7692)	(4.7926)	(4.7879)	(4.8361)

Zone Dummy	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Observations	5,864	5,864	5,864	5,864
R2	0.3992	0.4003	0.4003	0.3793
Adjusted R2	0.3915	0.3931	0.3933	0.3723
F Statistic	51.2850***	55.2420***	57.7385***	54.4996***
=====				

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Looking at the results from Table 21 with regression results from Barley OPH (quintals per hectare) we can see the results from four model outputs. The first, “Full”, presents the results based on the model selection from the VSURF algorithm and includes zonal fixed effects (FE). The second, “Reduced”, narrows the variable selection while including critical non-linearity for variables such as elevation, and adds key variables. The third model, “Final”, represents the final selection of significant variables for estimation. The last model, “No AgSS”, omits all AgSS survey variables to demonstrate the ability of the model to predict yields on the basis of remotely sensed data and last years yields.

In Table 21 we can see an impressive adjusted R^2 of 0.39. Residuals are also relatively small with 1st and 3rd quintiles spanning -4.78 and 3.85 quintals per hectare. Although interpretation is complex for this prediction-oriented model, most variables have the expected sign and significance. We can see that increased maximum and 90th percentile greenness during the growing season (G_mx, G_Qnt) corresponds to significantly higher yields ($p < 0.0512$ and $8.65e-08$ respectively). Interestingly, controlling for precipitation and growing season greenness the annual maximum greenness A_max_Qnt is negatively related to yields ($p < 3.02e-07$). This could be related to differences between dual and single crop areas. This however should be investigated further. Variability in precipitation during the Meher season PPT_G_sd has a negative but insignificant effect on yields ($p < 0.405$), while higher precipitation variability during the entire year PPT_A_sd increases yields ($p < 0.0495$). These findings likely point to the desirability of a consistent Meher rainy season, but more importantly to critical role the Belg rains play in soil moisture availability for both growing seasons. We can also see that the sum of precipitation across the Meher season $PPT_G_AUC_Qnt$ significantly increases yields ($p < 0.00723$), while having a higher maximum observed rainfall during that season $PPT_G_mx_Qnt$ can reduce yields ($p < 0.0258$) through greater damage to crops.

Looking at AgSS variables we can see the negative impacts of reported damage $BARLEYDAM_AGEAREA_P$ ($p < 4.03e-50$) and the positive impacts of increasing the coverage area of chemical fertilizers $BARLEYFERT_CHEMICAL_AREA$ ($p < 3.67e-06$)

Table 22: Panel RE regression on output per hectare for teff in quintals

Panel RE regression

=====				
Dependent variable:				

	TEFFOPH_W			
	Full	Reduced	Final	No AgSS
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)

TEFFOPH_W, 1)	0.2873***	0.2873***	0.2882***	0.3113***
	(0.0109)	(0.0109)	(0.0108)	(0.0110)
G_mx_Qnt	-0.0001			
	(0.0036)			
G_AUC_diff_mn	0.000004	0.000003		
	(0.00001)	(0.00001)		
G_AUC_Qnt	0.00001*	0.00001***	0.00001***	0.00001**
	(0.00001)	(0.000003)	(0.000003)	(0.000003)
A_sd	0.0020***	0.0022***	0.0023***	0.0029***
	(0.0004)	(0.0003)	(0.0003)	(0.0003)
A_max_Qnt	0.0002			
	(0.0039)			
T_G_Qnt	0.0001			
	(0.0004)			
PPT_G_AUC	-0.0004			
	(0.0006)			
PPT_G_AUC_trailing	-0.0002			
	(0.0003)			
PPT_G_sd	0.0273	0.0190		
	(0.0207)	(0.0168)		
PPT_G_mx_Qnt	-0.0118**	-0.0079		
	(0.0060)	(0.0058)		
PPT_G_AUC_Qnt	0.0019**	0.0015**	0.0013**	0.0018***
	(0.0008)	(0.0006)	(0.0006)	(0.0006)
PET_A_sd	-0.0151**	-0.0155**	-0.0167***	-0.0223***
	(0.0063)	(0.0062)	(0.0061)	(0.0062)
PPT_T_G_Qnt	-0.0336**	-0.0331**	-0.0328***	-0.0299**
	(0.0149)	(0.0147)	(0.0126)	(0.0128)
TEFFDAMAGEAREA_P	-7.2108***	-7.0764***	-7.0871***	
	(0.4368)	(0.4351)	(0.4349)	
TEFFFERT_CHEMICAL_AMT	0.0001	0.0003**	0.0003**	
	(0.0001)	(0.0001)	(0.0001)	
Fert_Amt_Per_Area		-0.0010**	-0.0010**	
		(0.0005)	(0.0005)	
TEFFAREA	0.1034***	0.0807***	0.0805***	
	(0.0148)	(0.0163)	(0.0163)	
Y_COORD	-0.000004*	-0.000003*	-0.000003*	-0.000005**
	(0.000002)	(0.000002)	(0.000002)	(0.000002)
X_COORD	0.00001***	0.00001***	0.00001***	0.00001***
	(0.000002)	(0.000002)	(0.000002)	(0.000002)
dist_pp50k	0.000001			
	(0.000003)			
dist_rcap	0.00001**	0.00001***	0.00001***	0.00001**
	(0.000002)	(0.000002)	(0.000002)	(0.000002)
elevation	0.0019***			
	(0.0002)			
bs(elevation, 3)1		-6.2332***	-6.3313***	-5.1210**

		(2.0305)	(2.0264)	(2.0549)
bs(elevation, 3)2		6.8509***	6.8793***	9.3317***
		(0.8863)	(0.8823)	(0.8802)
bs(elevation, 3)3		-2.7897*	-2.9933*	-3.4363**
		(1.6085)	(1.6004)	(1.6195)
c(Year)	0.6047***	0.5814***	0.5414***	0.4335***
	(0.0597)	(0.0587)	(0.0478)	(0.0484)
Constant	0.1557	4.5775	5.0360	5.6933*
	(3.3280)	(3.2890)	(3.2636)	(3.3054)

Zone Dummy	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Observations	7,373	7,373	7,373	7,373
R2	0.3039	0.3094	0.3100	0.2819
Adjusted R2	0.2965	0.3024	0.3033	0.2753
F Statistic	41.3527***	44.1837***	46.1929***	42.8010***
=====				

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

In Table 22 we can see an impressive adjusted R^2 of 0.3. Residuals are also relatively small with 1st and 3rd quintiles spanning -4.42 and 3.1 quintals per hectare. Although interpretation is complex for this prediction-oriented model, most variables have the expected sign and significance. We can see that increased sum of greenness during the growing season (G_AUC_Qnt) corresponds to significantly higher yields ($p<0.000385$). Similar to barley we see an increase in yields corresponding to higher annual variability but this time in greenness A_sd ($p<0.000385$), here we assume again this has to do with better performance in areas with a strong Belg rain. We also see an increase in yields corresponding to higher total rainfall across the growing season $PPT_G_AUC_Qnt$ ($p<0.0425$), and lower yields in areas with higher annual variability in rainfall PET_A_sd ($p<0.00625$). Looking at the basis splines for elevation $bs(elevation, i)$, teff is one of the few crops that seems to have a highly non-linear response where yields decline in low-land and upper highland areas.

Looking at AgSS variables we can see the positive impact of chemical fertilizers with $TEFF_FERT_CHEMICAL_AMT$ ($p<0.0356$), but interestingly a negative influence from higher fertilizer amounts per unit area $Fert_Amt_Per_Area$ ($p<0.0413$). Although this should be evaluated much further this might point to overly intensive use of chemical fertilizers in teff growing areas. This may be confirmed by the finding that yields improve with greater distance to regional capitals $dist_rcap$ ($p<0.00155$). This might confirm the finding with fertilizers since more rural areas would have limited access to input markets, thereby reducing their utilization of fertilizers etc.

Table 23: Panel RE regression on output per hectare for sorghum in quintals

Panel RE regression

Dependent variable:				
	SORGHUMOPH_W			
	Full	Reduced	Final	No AgSS
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
SORGHUMOPH_W, 1)	0.2571*** (0.0135)	0.2585*** (0.0135)	0.2591*** (0.0134)	0.2592*** (0.0137)
A_Qnt	0.0016*** (0.0004)	0.0016*** (0.0004)	0.0017*** (0.0002)	0.0024*** (0.0002)
G_mn	0.0002 (0.0003)	0.0002 (0.0003)		
PPT_T_G_Qnt	-0.0084 (0.0147)	-0.0085 (0.0147)		
PET_A_min	-0.0010 (0.0036)			
SORGHUMDAMAGEAREA_P	-9.5630*** (0.7066)	-9.5516*** (0.7049)	-9.5357*** (0.7043)	
SORGHUMFERT_CHEMICAL_AMT	-0.00002 (0.0002)			
Fert_Amt_Per_Area		0.0003 (0.0010)		
Y_COORD	0.00001** (0.000004)	0.00001** (0.000004)	0.00001** (0.000004)	0.00001** (0.000004)
X_COORD	0.00001*** (0.000004)	0.00001*** (0.000004)	0.00001*** (0.000004)	0.00001*** (0.000004)
dist_rcap	0.00001 (0.000005)	0.00001 (0.000005)	0.00001 (0.000004)	0.000001 (0.000004)
elevation	-0.0016*** (0.0004)			
bs(elevation, 3)1		-1.1277 (4.4048)	-1.1653 (4.3909)	-0.3590 (4.4724)
bs(elevation, 3)2		-2.9179 (2.5588)	-2.9431 (2.5297)	-2.4572 (2.5762)
bs(elevation, 3)3		-3.8284 (5.0268)	-3.9930 (5.0174)	-3.1931 (5.1099)
c(Year)	0.8416*** (0.0856)	0.8323*** (0.0795)	0.8378*** (0.0786)	0.7175*** (0.0795)
Constant	-9.8415 (6.2913)	-11.1115* (6.4818)	-11.4730* (6.4577)	-15.4878** (6.5710)
Region Dummy	Yes	No	No	No
Zone Dummy	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	5,108	5,108	5,113	5,113
R2	0.3066	0.3083	0.3083	0.2827
Adjusted R2	0.2977	0.2992	0.2997	0.2739
F Statistic	34.3031***	34.0366***	35.7203***	32.1070***

Note:

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

In Table 23 we can see an impressive adjusted R^2 of 0.3. Residuals are also relatively small with 1st and 3rd quintiles spanning -6.5 and 5.16 quintals per hectare. Although interpretation is complex for this prediction-oriented model, most variables have the expected sign and significance. We can see that increased 90th percentile of greenness during the growing season (A_Qnt) corresponds to significantly higher yields ($p<7.78e-14$). Interestingly we see no improvements from the amount $SORGHUMFERT_CHEMICAL_AMT$ or intensity $Fert_Amt_Per_Area$ of chemical fertilizer use for sorghum ($p<0.914$ and $p<0.752$ respectively).

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